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edited by

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Foreword

In 2026, with the beginning of construction of the Romanian components of the DANUBIUS-RI European Research Infrastructure, the National Institute of R&D for Biological Sciences Bucharest (INCDSB), coordinator of the DANUBIUS-RO Consortium, launched the first edition of the DANUBIUS-RI Scientific Conference. The event marks an important milestone in the development of the infrastructure and provides a framework for scientific dialogue in research fields related to river–sea systems and transitional environments.

As the institution coordinating the DANUBIUS-RI Hub, the Analysis Node, and the Danube Delta Supersite, INCDSB aims to highlight the infrastructure’s contribution to interdisciplinary research on global change, water resources, sediments, ecosystems, and river–sea systems. The conference also provides a platform for presenting research and exchanging ideas among researchers, experts, and infrastructure users, reflecting the interdisciplinary nature of INCDSB’s activities and its relevance to the DANUBIUS-RI research agenda. By bringing together researchers from the life sciences, Earth sciences, environmental sciences, engineering, and related disciplines, the event supports a scientific community focused on integrated approaches to river–sea system challenges.

The first edition is a national event intended to engage the Romanian research community around the objectives of DANUBIUS-RI. Beginning in 2027, the conference will become an international event, reflecting DANUBIUS-RI’s status as a pan-European research infrastructure and Romania’s role in coordinating and hosting several strategic components.

The conference is organised in partnership with the National University of Science and Technology POLITEHNICA Bucharest, which is involved, together with INCDSB and seven other national partners, in implementing the project “Support for the Development and Consolidation of DANUBIUS-RO.” This collaboration strengthens links between the research and academic communities and promotes the infrastructure’s opportunities for education, training, and research.

The involvement of POLITEHNICA Bucharest extends the conference’s reach to undergraduate, master’s, and doctoral students, for whom DANUBIUS-RI represents an opportunity to conduct research within a European infrastructure dedicated to river–sea systems. Through its facilities, services, and international collaborations, DANUBIUS-RI supports interdisciplinary projects and helps train a new generation of researchers.

The DANUBIUS-RI Scientific Conference aims to become a reference event for the scientific community interested in the processes and interactions that characterise river–sea systems. By bringing together researchers, students, and stakeholders, it supports national and international cooperation and the effective use of opportunities provided by the DANUBIUS-RI research infrastructure.

Mihaela Paun
General Director
INCDSB

08:30 – 09:00	Registration	
09:00 – 10:30	Opening Talks	
Mihaela Păun	INCDSB — <i>Welcoming Remarks</i>	
Mihai Dimian	Ministry of Education and Research	
Sorin Costreie	Presidential Advisor for Education and Research	
Mihnea Costoiu	Rector, University POLITEHNICA of Bucharest	
Andrei Alexandru	President, National Authority for Research	
Tudor Prisecaru	Vice President, National Authority for Research	
Mădălin Bunoiu	President, CCCDI	
Viorel Vulturescu	DANUBIUS-ERIC General Assembly Chair	
10:30 – 11:00	Coffee Break	
PRIORITY 01	Water Quantity	Moderator: Adrian Stănică
11:00 – 11:30	KEYNOTE Traian Ghibuş Technical University of Civil Engineering Bucharest (UTCB) <i>Innovative Solutions for the Use of Alternative Water Resources and Supporting Strategic Urban Planning Processes through Green Infrastructure Distribution Optimization</i>	
11:30 – 11:45	Manuela Sidoroff National Institute of R&D for Biological Sciences (INCDSB) <i>Bioinformatics — Bridges Between Science and Life: A Tribute to Solomon Marcus and Grigore Moisil in the Context of the International Centre DANUBIUS-RI</i>	
11:45 – 12:00	Laura Duşu National R&D Institute for Marine Geology and Geoecology (GeoEcoMar) <i>Hydrologic Connectivity in the Danube Delta</i>	
12:00 – 12:15	Andrei Toma National R&D Institute for Marine Geology and Geoecology (GeoEcoMar) <i>Spatially adaptive water occurrence mapping from Sentinel-1 using behaviour-stratified long-term backscatter statistics</i>	
PRIORITY 02	Sediment Balance	Moderator: Bogdan Oancea
12:15 – 12:45	KEYNOTE Adrian Stănică National R&D Institute for Marine Geology and Geoecology (GeoEcoMar) <i>The impact of the reduction of sediment flows on the Danube on the dynamics of the deltaic coastline</i>	
12:45 – 13:00	Iulian Nichersu Danube Delta National Institute for Research and Development (INCDDD) <i>Integrated Multi-Sensor Hydrographic Monitoring and Sediment Dynamics Assessment at the Danube–Black Sea Interface within the DANSER Project</i>	
13:00 – 13:15	Ioan Munteanu Institute of Geodynamics of the Romanian Academy (Geodin) <i>Sediments routes from their source to the sink: the Western Black Sea Basin</i>	
13:15 – 13:30	Maria Ionescu National R&D Institute for Marine Geology and Geoecology (GeoEcoMar) <i>Linking aerophotogrammetry and in-situ GNSS observations to assess shoreline change and sediment balance at Sfântu Gheorghe, Danube Delta, Romania</i>	
13:30 – 14:30	Lunch Break	

PRIORITY 03		Nutrients and Pollutants	Moderator: Venera Dobrică
14:30 – 15:00	KEYNOTE	Bogdan Bucur National Institute of R&D for Biological Sciences (INCDSB) <i>Butyrylcholinesterase biosensor for guanitoxin screening in cyanobacterial blooms</i>	
15:00 – 15:15		Dan Vasiliu Institute of Geodynamics of the Romanian Academy (Geodin) <i>Nutrient and Chlorophyll Dynamics on the Romanian Black Sea Shelf under the Direct Influence of the Danube River</i>	
15:15 – 15:30		Adriana Isvoran West University of Timișoara (UVT) <i>Ecotoxicological Assessment of Organic Contaminants Accumulated in the Iron Gates Reservoir System Along the Danube River</i>	
15:30 – 15:45		Irina Cătianis National R&D Institute for Marine Geology and Geoecology (GeoEcoMar) <i>Geochemical Dynamics of Danube Delta Sediments: A 2024 Seasonal Study of Key Fluvial-Lacustrine Zones</i>	
15:45 – 18:00		Coffee & Poster Session	

DAY 2 / TUESDAY, 8 JULY 2026

09:00 – 09:30	<i>Welcome Coffee & Day 2 Opening Remarks</i>		
PRIORITY 04		Climate Change	Moderator: Mihaela Păun
09:30 – 10:00	KEYNOTE	Maria Paraschiv National Institute of R&D for Biological Sciences (INCDSB) <i>DANUBIUS-RO Research Hub: Connecting Advanced Laboratories to Address Global Environmental Change</i>	
10:00 – 10:15		Venera Dobrică Institute of Geodynamics of the Romanian Academy (Geodin) <i>Large-Scale Climate Variability Modes and Lower Danube Discharge</i>	
10:15 – 10:30		Daria Voiculescu National Institute of R&D for Biological Sciences (INCDSB) <i>Wildfires in the Danube Delta Biosphere Reserve: Satellite-Based Burned Area Mapping and Wildlife Habitat Impact Assessment</i>	
10:30 – 10:45		Gabriel Lupu Danube Delta National Institute for Research and Development (INCDDD) <i>Invasive Alien Species Observatory and Network Development for the Assessment of Climate Change Impacts and Contextual Ecosystem Services Evaluation in Black Sea Deltaic — IASON+</i>	
10:45 – 11:00		Alexandru Costan UPB <i>Revisiting Reproducibility in Federated Learning across the Edge-Cloud Continuum: From Simulation to Cloud-Native Scheduling for Environmental Applications</i>	
PRIORITY 05		Extreme Events	Moderator: Sandra Eremia
11:00 – 11:30	KEYNOTE	Dorina Podar Babeș-Bolyai University (UBB) <i>Nature-based solutions to increase system resilience</i>	
11:30 – 11:45		Theodor-Radu Grumeza West University of Timișoara (UVT) <i>Integrated Satellite and Drone Monitoring for Wildfire Prevention</i>	
11:45 – 12:00		Omid Bornay Zonouzi Technical University of Civil Engineering Bucharest (UTCB) <i>Modeling the rain runoff process in order to obtain an optimal distribution of NbS in an urban district of Bucharest</i>	

PRIORITY 06		Protecting and Restoring Ecosystems & Biodiversity	Moderator: <i>Maria Paraschiv</i>
12:00 – 12:30	KEYNOTE	Mihai Adamescu University of Bucharest (UniBuc) <i>Restoring the Living Danube: From Biodiversity Protection to Systemic River–Wetland Recovery</i>	
12:30 – 12:45		Nicoleta Ianovici West University of Timișoara (UVT) <i>Success Mechanisms of Invasive Plant Species in the Danube Basin: Physiological Traits, Ecological Impact, and Their Role in Environmental Quality Monitoring</i>	
12:45 – 13:00		Avar-Lehel Dénes Babeș-Bolyai University (UBB) <i>Genetic diversity assessment of aquatic macroinvertebrates from a biodiversity hotspot in Romania</i>	
13:00 – 13:15		Marian Necula National Institute of R&D for Biological Sciences (INCDSB) <i>Mapping illegal fishing events from news media for the Romanian Danube Basin</i>	
13:15 – 13:30		Georgiana-Alexandra Grigore National Institute of R&D for Biological Sciences (INCDSB) <i>Exploring Psychrotolerant Bacterial Diversity Across Antarctic Aquatic Microniches During the ROICE2026 Expedition</i>	
13:30 – 13:45		Denisa Igescu University of Bucharest (UniBuc) <i>Linking environmental heterogeneity to freshwater microbial community assembly</i>	
13:45 – 14:30		Lunch Break	
PRIORITY 07		Digital Twin	Moderator: <i>Eduard Milea</i>
14:30 – 15:00	KEYNOTE	Ciprian Dobre University POLITEHNICA of Bucharest (UPB) <i>From data to knowledge creation — making use of DANUBIUS through emerging technologies</i>	
15:00 – 15:15		Cătălin Negru / Taisia Coconu University POLITEHNICA of Bucharest (UPB) <i>Computing Continuum Platform for River-Sea Systems</i>	
15:15 – 15:30		Bogdan-Costel Mocanu / Alex Deonise University POLITEHNICA of Bucharest (UPB) <i>Monitoring and logging service for natural resources: new trends and challenges</i>	
15:30 – 15:45		Adriana Olteanu University POLITEHNICA of Bucharest (UPB) <i>Digital Twin Framework for River-Sea Systems: A Hybrid Machine Learning and Rule-Based Water Quality Classification Approach</i>	
15:45 – 16:00		Daniela-Nicoleta Martin University POLITEHNICA of Bucharest (UPB) <i>A Multi-Level Data Preprocessing Solution for Environmental Sensor Data Integration in Digital Twin Environments</i>	
16:00 – 16:15		Teodora Minculescu Technical University of Civil Engineering Bucharest (UTCB) <i>From Urban Digital Twins to River-Sea Supersites: A Multi-Scale Geospatial Framework for Integrated Environmental Monitoring</i>	
16:15 – 17:00		Conclusions and Final Remarks	

Discussion Notes

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Abstracts

The background features a stylized, light blue illustration of a river system. At the top, a dam with a spillway is shown. The river flows downwards and then curves to the right. Several small markers are placed along the river: a teal dot near the dam, a yellow dot on a tributary, and a teal dot on the main river. Arrows indicate the direction of flow. A dashed line represents a boundary or path. A circle highlights a specific area on the right side of the river.

Priority 01 - Water Quantity

Spatially Adaptive Water Occurrence Mapping from Sentinel-1 Using Behaviour-Stratified Long-Term Backscatter Statistics

Andrei Toma^{1,2,3}; Ionut Sandric²; Bogdan-Andrei Mihai²; Albert Scriciu¹; Sabin Rotaru^{1,3}

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Sentinel-1 SAR enables cloud-independent surface water monitoring at high temporal frequency, yet threshold-based water classification over wetlands with heterogeneous land cover remains prone to spatially variable commission and omission errors when a single global backscatter threshold is applied uniformly. Existing long-term SAR archives contain the information needed to characterise the backscatter behaviour of individual pixels across the full range of hydrological conditions, but this multi-year record is rarely used to spatially stratify the classification itself. This study asks whether per-pixel long-term backscatter statistics derived from the same archive used for classification can replace a single global threshold with a spatially adaptive scheme that reduces false detections in dry low-backscatter environments without compromising water detection sensitivity in frequently inundated areas.

1. To derive spatially explicit, per-pixel classification thresholds from long-term Sentinel-1 VV backscatter statistics, the temporal median and the tenth percentile, calibrated against stable reference classes from the JRC Global Surface Water Occurrence product using the Youden J criterion.
2. To construct a binary zone mask from the long-term P10 backscatter raster and implement a zone-adaptive two-threshold classification scheme that applies the median threshold in water-prone areas and the P10 threshold in not-water areas.
3. To evaluate the zone-adaptive classification against two independent reference datasets representing complementary temporal regimes: the JRC Monthly Surface Water product over 55 months (2015-2021) and Dynamic World over 107 months (2016-2024), with performance assessed globally, by zone, and within a targeted dune area of interest.
4. To produce a per-pixel water occurrence map for the Romanian Danube Delta by accumulating binary classifications across the full ten-year Sentinel-1 archive and characterise the resulting inundation frequency distribution across hydrological classes.

The study area is the Romanian Danube Delta, a low-gradient alluvial delta with a mosaic of open water, reed beds, flooded forest, and sandy coastal environments. Sentinel-1 GRD scenes in VV polarisation were processed using the Analysis-Ready Data framework in Google Earth Engine, with preprocessing comprising border noise correction, mono-temporal Gamma-MAP speckle filtering, and radiometric terrain normalisation.

Two long-term per-pixel backscatter descriptors, the temporal median and the temporal tenth percentile (P10), were computed from the full 2015-2024 archive. Thresholds were calibrated by intersecting both rasters with stable reference classes from the JRC Global Surface Water Occurrence product (0% occurrence as not-water, 95-100% as permanent water) and selecting the backscatter value that maximises the Youden J statistic. The P10 threshold was applied to the P10 raster to generate a binary zone mask separating water-prone from not-water areas, and classification was subsequently performed using the median threshold in water-prone pixels and the P10 threshold elsewhere.

Monthly composites were generated using a maximum backscatter operator for comparison with the JRC Monthly Surface Water product, and individual acquisitions were paired with Dynamic World scenes within a three-day temporal window. The per-pixel water occurrence map was derived by computing the ratio of water detections to valid observations across all acquisitions in the archive. Performance was evaluated against both reference datasets using pixel-wise confusion matrices derived from stratified random samples of 5 000 pixels per month, with metrics including F1-score, MCC, precision, recall, and specificity computed monthly and pooled. Evaluation was conducted

globally, stratified by behavioural zone, and within a targeted dune mask derived from the Corine Land Cover class for beaches, dunes, and sand plains, where three classification strategies, the global median threshold, the global P10 threshold, and the zone-adaptive scheme, were compared to quantify the reduction in false detections over dry low-backscatter surfaces.

The zone-adaptive classification achieved consistent agreement with both reference datasets across a ten-year archive. Against the JRC Monthly Surface Water product over 55 months (2015-2021), the mean F1-score was 0.839 (SD = 0.054) and mean MCC was 0.815. Against Dynamic World over 107 months (2016-2024), mean F1 was 0.801 (SD = 0.106) and mean MCC was 0.778. Zone-stratified evaluation showed that performance is strongly structured by land cover context: in water-prone areas, median water recall exceeded 0.93 across both datasets, while specificity in not-water areas remained above 0.98, reflecting the effect of applying the more conservative P10 threshold where dry surfaces dominate. In dune areas, the adaptive strategy reduced median commission error from 0.661 to 0.112 against JRC and from 0.258 to 0.012 against Dynamic World, while maintaining water recall at 0.996 and 0.850 respectively, confirming that spatial stratification suppresses false detections without sacrificing sensitivity in genuinely inundated pixels. Applying the global P10 threshold achieved comparable commission error reductions but at the cost of substantially lower water recall (0.953 against JRC, 0.574 against Dynamic World), demonstrating that the zone-adaptive scheme is the only strategy that controls false detections while preserving detection sensitivity.

The accumulated occurrence map reveals a strongly bimodal inundation frequency distribution. Of the 3 588 km² study area, 64.8% was never classified as water across the full archive, while 21.8% fell in the episodic class (1-10% occurrence frequency), concentrated at the lowest frequencies and reflecting inundation limited to rare high-discharge events. Transitional pixels (11-75%) accounted for only 2.9% of the area, consistent with the abrupt topographic transitions characteristic of alluvial delta morphology. Permanent and highly permanent water (above 75% occurrence) covered 10.5% of the study area, with the highly permanent class concentrated between 90% and 96% occurrence, corresponding to open lakes and main river channels with stable bathymetry. The divergence between the mean (32.9%) and median (3%) occurrence across water-bearing pixels captures the distributional asymmetry of inundation frequency in the delta.

The zone-adaptive two-threshold framework demonstrates that long-term per-pixel backscatter statistics derived from the same Sentinel-1 archive used for classification can replace a single global threshold with a spatially explicit scheme that reduces commission errors in dry low-backscatter environments without compromising water detection sensitivity. The consistency of results across two independent reference datasets with contrasting temporal characteristics, one monthly and Landsat-derived, the other near-real-time and Sentinel-2-derived, increases confidence in the robustness of the approach across different validation regimes and time periods.

The per-pixel occurrence map produced from the ten-year archive provides a baseline characterisation of inundation frequency in the Danube Delta that is not available from any single-date or annual composite product. The strongly bimodal distribution, with a large episodic class concentrated at the lowest occurrence frequencies and a permanent water network where most pixels cluster between 90% and 96% occurrence, reflects the sharp topographic transitions of alluvial delta morphology and has direct relevance for flood risk assessment, wetland habitat mapping, and hydrological connectivity analysis.

The framework requires no external land cover data and is calibrated entirely from the SAR archive itself, which makes it applicable to other wetland systems where long Sentinel-1 records now exist but ancillary thematic maps are absent or outdated. A practical limitation is that the zone mask and thresholds are derived from the historical archive and may not track rapid land cover change; recalibration would be needed if the study period is extended substantially or applied to a different region. The availability of Sentinel-1C since late 2024 and the planned Sentinel-1D launch ensures archive continuity, and extension of the framework to include cross-polarisation channels or flooded vegetation detection using longer-wavelength sensors such as ROSE-L represents a natural direction for future work.

Keywords: Water Occurrence; Sentinel-1; Spatially Adaptive Classification

This work was supported by a grant of the Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digitization, CNCS/CCCDI - UEFISCDI, project number PN-IV-P8-8.1-PRE-HE-ORG-2023-0089, within PNCDI IV. Andrei Toma acknowledges support from the Council for Doctoral Studies (CSUD), University of Bucharest.

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

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Hydrologic Connectivity in the Danube Delta

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One of the most important roles in ensuring the good functionality of a deltaic system is played by hydrological connectivity, a concept developed by hydrologists to better understand the importance for water quantity and quality. Human activities, such as landscape engineering, construction of reservoirs, and hydrotechnical works, play an important role by segmentation or even interruption of the freshwater transfer in the fluvial systems. Particularly, the artificial cutoffs eliminate the threat of flood caused by the meandering river, but it significantly changes its hydro-morphological and sedimentological regime.

Multiple series of human works (such as meander bends cut-offs, construction of dikes, jetties, groins, construction of a very large network of canals, river bank stabilization, and substitution of natural ecosystems into large polders) have influenced the hydrological connectivity in the Danube Delta system. Along Sulina and St. George distributaries, a series of free meanders were rectified to facilitate navigation. As effect, most of the natural channels are heavily clogged, and the former meanders become seasonally or permanently isolated from the main distributary. The artificial canals were intensively eroded, while the former meanders are going to be progressively sedimented.

The purpose of this study is to present specific aspects concerning the hydrological connectivity in the Danube Delta and to reveal the role of various control factors highlight the spatial and temporal variability of the water flows and the influence of some control variables (such as climatic changes and human activities). Complex investigations on many sub-systems (river-channel-lake site type) formed by cutoff meanders, connective channels, and lakes along the Sulina and Saint George branches have been performed to observe how much the water and sediment inputs to the delta depressions are affected by the structural changes of the meander physiography.

Keywords: Hydrologic Connectivity; Danube Delta; ADCP; Human Activities

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The authors declare no conflict of interest.

The background features a stylized, light blue illustration of a river system with winding channels and tributaries. Small blue and brown dots representing sediment are scattered throughout the water and along the banks. In the lower half of the image, a balance scale is depicted, with two circular pans on either side of a central fulcrum. The left pan is lower and contains more sediment, while the right pan is higher and contains less. A vertical dashed line extends from the fulcrum down to the riverbed below, suggesting a connection between the sediment balance and the river's physical structure.

Priority 02 - Sediment Balance

Sediment Routes from Their Source to the Sink in the Western Black Sea Basin

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The basin fill encodes the geological history of the processes responsible for the formation of the accommodation space and those responsible for fill in with the sediments. Deciphering the sedimentary records can provide clues on the evolution of the sedimentary fluxes from the source areas, the transport processes and the balance between the creation and reduction/fill of the accommodation space. The Western Black Sea Basin opened during Cretaceous as a back-arc basin due to the N-ward subduction of the Neotethys oceanic plate, rifting continued during Upper Cretaceous-Paleogene time with the separation of two distinct basins West and East. The Middle Eocene continental collision of the Pontides with Taurides, gradually inverted the former extensional structures of the Black Sea Basin, during Late Eocene-Pliocene times, generating a bi-vergent thrust system in the basin margins, N-ward in the Western and S-ward in the Eastern sub-basin, with a large transfer zone defined by the Odessa-West Crimean Fault system and Andrusov Ridge system. In the same time basins center recorded regional scale subsidence with the deposition of thick sedimentary succession separated by several unconformities or their correlative surfaces.

For understanding the evolution of the sedimentary fluxes into the NW part of the Black Sea self a detailed seismic and sequence stratigraphy study has been performed.

The analysis shows the existence of sediments entry points from the nearby Carpathian foreland into the Black Sea main sink during Paleogene-Pliocene times. Their geometry and evolution was strongly influenced by the tectonic uplifted structures during Paleogene-Pliocene times, and by rapid Western Black Sea basin subsidence during Pliocene-Quaternary, coeval with the final filling of the Carpathian foreland basin the so-called Dacian Basin, and hence the shifting of sedimentary fluxes towards Black Sea.

Keywords: Black Sea; Seismic; Sequence Stratigraphy

Integrated Multi-Sensor Hydrographic Monitoring and Sediment Dynamics Assessment at the Danube-Black Sea Interface within the DANSER Project

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The Danube-Black Sea transition zone is one of Europe's most dynamic sedimentary environments, where hydrological variability, anthropogenic pressures, dredging activities, and climate change significantly influence sediment transport, water quality, ecosystem connectivity, and biodiversity. Within the Horizon Europe project DANSER (DANube SEDiment Restoration), an integrated multidisciplinary framework is being developed to improve the understanding and sustainable management of sediment dynamics across the Danube River Basin and its coastal interface.

This contribution presents an advanced multi-sensor hydrographic and environmental monitoring approach applied at the Danube-Black Sea interface.

The methodology combines high-resolution bathymetric surveys, Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ADCP) measurements, in situ physico-chemical profiling, sediment characterization, remote sensing products, and hydrodynamic modelling to investigate sediment transport pathways, plume dynamics, water-column stratification, and channel morphology evolution. By integrating field observations with numerical simulations and spatial analysis, the study evaluates interactions between sediment dynamics, ecological conditions, and water-quality gradients in riverine, transitional, and coastal environments.

DANSER further integrates geomorphological investigations, biodiversity monitoring, GIS-based spatio-temporal mapping, and machine-learning-supported environmental analyses to support evidence-based sediment management strategies. The project develops innovative tools for sediment forecasting, contamination assessment, restoration planning, and sustainable dredged-material management, while promoting ecosystem resilience and climate adaptation. Particular emphasis is placed on reconnecting floodplains, improving ecological status, and supporting circular-economy approaches through sediment reuse and nature-based solutions.

Beyond the scientific and technical dimension, DANSER promotes stakeholder engagement, citizen science, technical training, and transnational cooperation through workshops, educational activities, and digital dissemination platforms. The project contributes directly to the objectives of the EU Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters," the European Green Deal, and several Sustainable Development Goals related to clean water, climate action, sustainable communities, and aquatic ecosystem restoration.

The presented approach demonstrates how integrated hydrographic monitoring and interdisciplinary environmental assessment can support sustainable sediment governance and strengthen river-sea connectivity at basin scale.

Keywords: Sediment Dynamics; Hydrographic Monitoring; Danube-Black Sea Interface

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Linking Aerophotogrammetry and in Situ GNSS Observations to Assess Shoreline Change and Sediment Balance at Sfantu Gheorghe, Danube Delta, Romania

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The Sfantu Gheorghe coastal sector, situated north of the mouth of the Sfantu Gheorghe branch of the Danube, represents a highly dynamic environment affected by shoreline migration, sediment redistribution and active coastal processes. This study integrates UAV-based aerophotogrammetry with in situ GNSS measurements to assess shoreline evolution and sediment budget changes between 2023 - and 2025.

High-resolution aerial surveys were conducted in July of each year using a DJI Mavic 3T platform following both nadir and oblique flight missions. A total of 4070 images were acquired over a coastal sector of approximately 0.032 km² and processed in Agisoft Metashape and Global Mapper to generate orthomosaics, dense point clouds, digital elevation models (DEMs) and digital terrain models (DTMs) with centimetric spatial accuracy. Ten ground control points (GCPs) were measured using a Trimble R4 system to ensure geometric calibration and orthorectification accuracy.

Sediment volumetric comparative analyses of DTMs from 2023 and 2024 revealed significant shoreline retreat, sediment erosion, and volumetric beach changes, particularly in the Cape Buival area. Elevation differences ranged from -1.5 m to +0.8 m, indicating predominantly erosional processes, while volumetric calculations showed a net sediment loss of approximately 1350 m³.

The sediment volumes comparative analyses of DTMs from 2024 and 2025 revealed an intensification of coastal erosion and measurable volumetric changes in beach morphology. The results indicate dominant erosional trends across the study area, with elevation differences ranging from -1.2 m to +1.8 m. Volumetric analyses indicated a markedly higher net sediment loss of approximately 7095 m³.

GNSS-based beach and shoreline measurements validated the patterns identified through UAV-derived terrain models. The findings indicate that coastal dynamics in the Sfantu Gheorghe beach sector are strongly controlled by interactions at the Danube-Black Sea confluence, leading to complex patterns of sediment redistribution at the river-sea interface.

The integration of high-resolution UAV aerophotogrammetry with in situ GPS coastal monitoring provides an effective and reliable framework for quantifying coastal morphological changes and sediment budget evolution in rapidly evolving river - delta - sea systems.

Keywords: DTM; Orthomosaic; UAV; Ground Control Points

Wetland Reconnection as a Nature-Based Solution for Sustainable Sediment Management in the Danube Delta: The Carasuhat Wetland Case Study

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Large areas of the Danube Delta were embanked and drained during the twentieth century for agricultural and economic purposes, leading to major alterations of natural hydrological connectivity, sediment dynamics, and wetland ecosystem functions. The transformation of former deltaic wetlands into enclosed polders reduced water and sediment retention capacity, contributed to habitat degradation, and affected the ecological resilience of the deltaic system. In recent years, wetland reconnection has become increasingly recognised as an effective Nature-Based Solution (NBS) for restoring hydromorphological processes and improving ecosystem services in river - sea systems.

The Carasuhat ecological restoration project represents one of the most significant wetland reconnection initiatives implemented in the Romanian Danube Delta. The project reconnected approximately 924 ha of former agricultural polder to the natural hydrological regime of the Danube Delta wetland system through controlled dyke breaching and the reactivation of former water circulation pathways.

This study aimed to characterise the current evolutionary state of the restored Carasuhat wetland through: (1) high-resolution single-beam bathymetric surveying for the generation of a detailed hypsometric map of the wetland floor; (2) measurements of water current velocities and flow discharges at the inlet and outlet channels connecting the wetland to the Danube River using an Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ADCP); and (3) acquisition of a high-resolution aerial orthophoto mosaic using UAV-based photogrammetry for the spatial delineation of wetland and terrestrial zones.

Bathymetric surveys were performed using a Cee-Line single-beam echosounder mounted on a survey boat, with transects spaced at approximately 100 m intervals and georeferenced using differential GPS positioning. Sound velocity corrections were applied based on in situ CTD measurements. Water current velocities and flow discharges were measured using an RD Instruments RiverRay ADCP deployed through rope-guided transects due to the reduced width of the connecting channels. At least three transect passes were performed for each cross-section, while measurements were accepted only when the coefficient of variation remained below 5%.

Aerial photogrammetric surveys were conducted using a DJI Inspire 2 UAV equipped with a Zenmuse X4S camera following systematic flight grids at constant altitude. The acquired geotagged imagery was processed to generate a high-resolution georeferenced orthomosaic of the restored wetland area.

Approximately 50 bathymetric profiles were acquired within the wetland. The resulting hypsometric map showed that the deepest sectors are associated with the western channel, consistent with dredging activities carried out in early 2021, while elevated bed levels identified in the south-south-eastern sector suggest active sediment deposition linked to Danube inflows. ADCP measurements at the inlet channel yielded a mean discharge of 5.28 m³/s (4 transects; standard deviation 0.29 m³/s; COV 5%), with a mean flow velocity of 0.19 m/s. At the outlet channel, the mean discharge was 8.3 m³/s (11 valid transects; standard deviation 0.88 m³/s), with a mean flow velocity of 0.27 m/s.

The UAV survey covered approximately 7.4 km² through nine UAV flights, producing a centimetric-resolution orthomosaic that clearly delineates open water surfaces, flooded margins, and terrestrial vegetation zones.

The integrated geophysical investigations demonstrated that, less than one year after restoration, the Carasuhat wetland was already exhibiting distinct morphological and hydrological patterns driven by both anthropogenic interventions and natural sedimentary processes associated with Danube

connectivity. The resulting dataset, including the high-resolution hypsometric map, quantified inlet and outlet discharges, and centimetric orthomosaic, provides a valuable baseline for future monitoring of hydromorphological evolution within the restored wetland system and supports future hydraulic modelling and adaptive wetland management initiatives.

Keywords: ADCP; Bathymetry; Discharge; Danube Delta; Carasuhat Wetland

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Understanding Shoreline Shifts Along Romania's Southern Black Sea Coast: A Multidecadal (1984-2024) Satellite-Based Analysis

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Coastal erosion and shoreline instability are growing concerns globally, driven by sea-level rise, reduced sediment supply, and intensive coastal engineering. Along Romania's southern Black Sea coast, a microtidal environment heavily modified by groynes, breakwaters, and large-scale beach nourishment, the long-term shoreline response to these interventions remains poorly quantified. No regionally consistent, validated, multi-decadal shoreline dataset previously existed for this coast, limiting evidence-based coastal management.

This study aims to: (1) develop and validate a multi-decadal satellite-derived shoreline dataset (1984-2024) for Romania's southern Black Sea coast; (2) quantify long-term shoreline change rates across nourished and non-nourished sectors; and (3) compare shoreline change behaviour and variability before and after beach nourishment interventions within a unified analytical framework.

Shoreline positions were extracted from Landsat 5/7/8/9 and Sentinel-2 imagery using the CoastSat toolkit and validated against in-situ GNSS measurements at seven sites. Shoreline change rates (Linear Regression Rate, LRR) were computed in DSAS using annually averaged shoreline positions derived via a two-step seasonal aggregation procedure. Non-parametric statistical tests (Kruskal-Wallis, Mann-Whitney U with Bonferroni correction, Levene's test) were applied to compare shoreline change behaviour across non-nourished, pre-nourishment, and post-nourishment groups.

Validation against GNSS data showed strong agreement ($R^2 > 0.85$ at multiple sites; best performance: $R^2 = 0.98$, $RMSE = 0.21$ m/yr). Non-nourished sectors were largely stable (mean LRR: -0.08 to +0.51 m/yr). Sandy foreshore sectors prior to nourishment were consistently accreting (mean LRR: +0.17 to +0.97 m/yr, low variability). Following nourishment, responses were heterogeneous: zones A2, A5, A6, and B1 shifted to erosional or near-stable conditions (mean LRR: -0.83 to -0.02 m/yr), while zones A3, A4, and A7 maintained positive rates (+0.22 to +0.87 m/yr). Post-nourishment variability increased substantially in most zones (post-BN STD: 0.38 to 1.20 m/yr vs. 0.16 to 0.79 m/yr pre-BN). Statistical analysis confirmed that post-nourishment groups exhibit significantly greater variability and lower median change rates than both pre-nourishment and non-nourished groups.

Satellite-derived shoreline monitoring reliably captures long-term shoreline dynamics along this microtidal coast. Beach nourishment does not produce a uniform shoreline response: while some sectors maintained or increased accretion, others shifted to erosion, with consistently elevated post-intervention variability. These findings highlight the importance of site-specific monitoring and adaptive management. The validated, reproducible workflow presented here provides a scalable framework for long-term coastal monitoring and evidence-based management in Romania and comparable engineered coastlines.

Keywords: Shoreline Change; Beach Nourishment; Satellite-Derived Shorelines; Coastal Monitoring; Microtidal Environment

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Study of the Ieselnita River from Morphometrical and Sedimentological Points of View

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Very little is known about the Iron Gates gorge of the Danube in terms of recent morphometrical and sedimentological patterns of the main stream network evolution. Preliminary insight into these matters was acquired by performing a thematic analysis of the catchment of Ieselnita, a Danube left side tributary in the gorge section.

The configuration of the main river channel is the result of changes that have occurred in the watershed under the influence of environmental factors. One of the factors taken into account is the topography, and its morphometric analysis makes it possible to identify the key factors in the formation of the channel pattern.

Stream order and chi plot [1] analysis are the morphometric methods used to determine the stage of evolution of the Ieselnita River. Stream order correlates with link length, drainage area, slope and channel size, providing a relative sense of physical conditions, but is sensitive to how one defines the channel pattern.

According to Horton Strahler classification [2] the Ieselnita River is a small to medium size, rank 5 to 6. The chi-transformed profiles showed that both the line corresponding to Ieselnita trunk stream and the lines of the collapsing tributaries were remarkably straight (the R2 value of the fitted linear regression was 0.998).

The Ieselnita River exhibits a clear longitudinal sedimentological evolution controlled by slope and stream power. In the upper sector (>550 m altitude), the channel corresponds to a bedload channel, with transport dominated by coarse bedload and a morphology close to straight. In the middle and submontane sector (550-300 m altitude), the flow becomes mixed-load, characterized by alternating erosion-deposition processes and meandering tendencies. In the lower sector (<300 to confluence with the Danube River), the channel transforms into a suspended-load channel, stabilized, with transport dominated by fine suspended material and a morphology once again straight, influenced by the backwater effect of the Danube.

The pattern of the chi plot analysis indicates that: the stream courses are in a steady state, i.e., the incision rate is perfectly balanced by the uplift rate, and no transient processes (like a change in the uplift rate or in the substratum erodibility), distorted the chi-plot pattern; the catchment is laterally uniform in terms of uplift rate and of substratum erodibility.

The transition of Ieselnita River from straight bedload upstream, to meandering mixed-load in the submontane zone, and back to straight suspended-load at the confluence reflects the altitudinal gradient control on the alluvial style of the Ieselnita River (in accordance with Schumm's classification [3]).

Keywords: Morphometrical Analysis; Sedimentological Pattern; Chi-Plot Pattern

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Recent Morphological and Sedimentological Processes in the Danube Delta

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Morphological processes of the fluvial channel are controlled by liquid and solid fluxes through hydraulic forces exerted by flow and sediment transport, erosion, and deposition. During the last centuries, many fluvial systems have been significantly affected by human interventions.

The Danube Delta represents an important natural system, located in the lower part of the Danube River. Moreover, the anthropogenic changes have significantly altered the hydraulic and sediment dynamics. On the Sulina and St. George branches, the meander cutoff programme induced different hydro-sedimentary impacts on the local distribution of river flow velocities, discharge, and sediment fluxes between the former meanders and the man-made canals. The diversion of the flow induces strong modifications by acceleration of the fluxes through the artificial canals, combined with dramatically enhanced deposition in the former meanders.

We present new data on the morphological and sedimentological processes along the rectified meanders of St. George branch, as an example to analyse the human impact in the Danube Delta. Morphological and sedimentological data were acquired throughout several cross sections of both natural channels and artificial canals of many cutoffs. 3D and 2D bathymetrical data were acquired and very fine details of the bed were analysed.

Keywords: Danube Delta; Bathymetry; Sediment Fluxes; Aggradation

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The authors declare no conflict of interest.

The background features a light blue, wavy river that meanders across the page. The river is composed of several overlapping, semi-transparent bands. Small, solid blue arrows are placed along the river's path, indicating the direction of flow. Interspersed among the river and in the surrounding white space are various clusters of small, light blue dots, some of which are connected by thin, dashed lines, suggesting the movement or distribution of nutrients and pollutants. The overall aesthetic is clean, modern, and scientific.

Priority 03 - Nutrients and Pollutants

Geochemical Dynamics of Danube Delta Sediments: A 2024 Seasonal Study of Key Fluvial-Lacustrine Zones

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Sediment geochemical dynamics in the Danube Delta exhibit spatial heterogeneity between bifurcations and lacustrine environments. Distinguishing whether trace metal enrichment stems from anthropogenic pollution or natural geogenic backgrounds is essential for environmental management. This 2024 study evaluates these dynamics across key bifurcations and the Rusca-Gorgova-Uzlina system during contrasting hydrological periods. We assessed the geochemical status of riverbed and lakebed sediments, characterized carbonate and TOC distributions, quantified toxic and technophilic metals, and distinguished geogenic enrichment from anthropogenic contamination to provide valuable insights for the Biosphere Reserve's sustainable management. Surface sediments were sampled during low-water (September 2024) and high-water (October 2024, post-flood) conditions. Analysis involved titration for CaCO₃ and TOC (Walkley-Black), ED-XRF for major and trace elements (Fe, Mn, Ti, As, Cr, Cu, Ni, Pb, Rb, Sr, V, Zn, Zr), and AAS for Hg. Results were compared against regulatory limits. Riverbed sediments were predominantly non-carbonate (<10% CaCO₃, <1% TOC), reflecting high-energy conditions. Lakebed sediments showed higher accumulation (up to 35% CaCO₃, 7% TOC) from low-energy deposition. Most toxic metals (As, Pb, Zn) remained below regulatory thresholds. Notably, Cr, Cu, and Ni exceedances were linked to natural geogenic backgrounds rather than human impact. Isolated Hg elevations occurred during low-water, while Sr, Ti, and Zr patterns were driven by hydrodynamic sorting and mineralogical provenance. The overall chemical status is acceptable; episodic exceedances do not indicate systemic pollution. Geochemical variability observed in this study is driven by hydrodynamic processes and natural mineralogy rather than anthropogenic pressure, highlighting the need for regular monitoring to maintain ecological integrity.

Keywords: Danube Delta; Environmental Monitoring; Fluvial-Lacustrine Transition; Seasonal Variability; Sediment Geochemistry; Trace Elements

Nutrient and Chlorophyll Dynamics on the Romanian Black Sea Shelf under the Direct Influence of the Danube River

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The Danube River serves as the primary source of anthropogenic and natural nutrient loading into the north-western Black Sea, yet the precise spatial boundaries of this fluvial plume remain highly dynamic. This study addresses how localized riverine discharge dictates modern eutrophication gradients and alters marine stratification during the critical late-spring to early-summer transition. Understanding these localized land-sea interactions is vital for assessing the immediate ecological resilience of the inner continental shelf against severe nutrient over-enrichment.

The primary objectives are to quantify the immediate impact of the Danube River plume on surface nutrient concentrations and to determine how river-induced turbidity and nutrient loading regulate the intensity of coastal algal blooms and the vertical distribution of the chlorophyll maximum.

Data were collected during an oceanographic cruise aboard the R/V Mare Nigrum (June 7-16, 2025) across 32 sampling stations. The experimental setup prioritized transects directly intersecting the river's plume (Sulina, Sfantu Gheorghe, and Portita) alongside southern reference transects (Constanta and Mangalia), covering depths from 13 m to 1116 m. Water column profiling of physical parameters was integrated with targeted laboratory analyses of nutrients and chlorophyll concentrations to map the river's footprint.

The direct footprint of the Danube was sharply defined in the surface layer of the inner shelf, where nutrient concentrations reached distinct peaks: PO₄ up to 0.38 μ M, SiO₄ up to 15.02 μ M, and NO₃ up to 27.37 μ M. The highest surface concentrations of nitrates and phosphates were concentrated at the Sulina mouth (station SU01), while nitrites, ammonium, and silicates peaked at the shallowest waters from the Portita bay (station PO01, confirming the river as the dominant nutrient source. This massive continental input triggered intense, localized algal blooms, driving surface chlorophyll to maximum values of 18.33 μ g/L (SU01) and 13.9 μ g/L (PO01). Furthermore, river-induced turbidity in the northern sector structurally altered the water column; high surface turbidity near the Danube delta restricted light penetration, suppressing the Subsurface Chlorophyll Maximum (SCM) to deeper offshore waters (>30 m), whereas the clearer, less influenced southern waters maintained a shallow SCM at 13 m.

The study demonstrates that the Danube River remains the dominant driver of eutrophication on the inner Black Sea shelf, fueling intense localized algal blooms. Furthermore, the sharp contrast in vertical chlorophyll distribution highlights how river-induced turbidity structurally alters pelagic primary productivity zones. These findings are crucial for regional water quality models and emphasize the need for continued monitoring of land-sea interactions to mitigate ecological degradation in the Black Sea basin.

Keywords: Black Sea; Danube River; Eutrophication

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The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Ecotoxicological Assessment of Organic Contaminants Accumulated in the Iron Gates Reservoir System Along the Danube River

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The Iron Gates (Portile de Fier) reservoir system represents a major accumulation zone for organic contaminants along the Danube River due to its high sediment retention capacity and altered hydrodynamics. More than 50% of incoming suspended solids are trapped within the reservoirs, promoting the deposition of fine sediments that efficiently adsorb and store hydrophobic pollutants. Previous investigations have documented a wide range of contaminants, including pharmaceuticals, pesticides, persistent organic pollutants, endocrine-disrupting compounds, and per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances within this system. During high-flow or flood events, sediment resuspension may remobilize these substances, transforming sediments from long-term sinks into secondary pollution sources.

The computational platforms admetSAR3.0 and ADMETLab3.0 were used to predict the ecotoxicological profiles of frequently detected contaminants in the Iron Gates area. The assessment focused on the pharmaceuticals sulfamethoxazole, erythromycin and diclofenac, as well as the herbicide terbuthylazine. Predicted toxicity endpoints were evaluated for multiple aquatic organisms representing different trophic levels.

Model outputs indicated that all four compounds may exert adverse effects on several aquatic species, including *Pseudokirchneriella subcapitata*, *Daphnia magna*, *Pimephales promelas*, *Lepomis macrochirus*, *Oncorhynchus mykiss*, *Cyprinodon variegatus* and *Tetrahymena pyriformis*. Among these, *T. pyriformis* appeared particularly sensitive to the tested substances. Additionally, terbuthylazine was predicted to pose a risk of human hepatotoxicity.

Computational predictions suggest that contaminants frequently detected in the Iron Gates reservoir system may negatively impact multiple aquatic organisms and, in the case of terbuthylazine, potentially human health. These findings highlight the need for targeted experimental validation and further monitoring to better understand contaminant behavior and ecological risks in this major Danube River reservoir system.

Keywords: Ecotoxicity; Aquatic Organism; Computational

Nutrients and Pollutants in River-Sea Systems: Bioanalytical Tools for Early Warning, Threshold Definition and Restoration Support

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River-sea systems are transitional environments where nutrient enrichment, chemical contamination, hydrological variability and sediment dynamics interact across spatial and temporal scales. In the Danube-Danube Delta-Black Sea continuum, these interactions are particularly relevant because nutrient loads, emerging pollutants, legacy contaminants and biological responses converge in a highly productive but vulnerable system.

This work proposes a bioanalytical framework for assessing the combined effects of nutrients and pollutants in water and biota.

The proposed approach builds on complementary analytical capacities, including chromatographic methods for nutrients, organic contaminants and emerging pollutants and electrochemical sensors and biosensors for rapid screening of contaminants and biologically active markers.

The capability of electrochemical sensors and biosensors to be used as early warning tools is presented and comparison with highly sensitive analytical techniques (chromatography with appropriate detection) is provided, highlighting the limitations with respect to sensitivity and resolution. The use of sensing devices and/or sensing arrays to assess the contamination patterns, nutrient-pollutant co-occurrence, potential toxicity hotspots and early-warning indicators of ecological stress is presented and examples including emerging pollutants - such as pharmaceuticals, endocrine disruptors, pesticides and transformation products-which require sensitive detection methods and integrated assessment of mixture effects are provided, underlining the analytical performances of developed sensors in terms of sensitivity and limit of detection: molecularly imprinted polymer (MIP) sensors based on Meldola Blue electropolymerised on screen-printed gold electrodes enabled selective quantification of PFOA at sub-nanomolar concentrations (LOD 0.63 nM); electrochemical sensors based on modified electrodes allowed detection of the endocrine-disrupting compound bisphenol A (BPA) at 1.15 nM (LOD). Both performances were validated against HPLC-MS reference methods across river water, agro-industrial lateral stream and food-contact leachate matrices; collectively, these platforms establish a methodological basis for threshold definition and restoration-support monitoring within integrated source-to-sea nutrient and pollutant surveillance frameworks.

The paper supports the idea that nutrient and pollutant assessment should move beyond single-parameter monitoring and adopt an integrated source-to-sea perspective, connecting river inputs, deltaic retention and transformation processes, sediment-water exchanges, and coastal impacts, underlining the efficacy of friendly-user analytical tools as sensors in the monitoring and early warning process. The proposed framework is intended to support understanding of nutrient-pollutant interactions and practical decision-making for restoration, pollution control of river-sea systems.

Keywords: Pollutants; Early Warning; Sensors

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The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Geochemical Dynamics of Danube Delta Sediments: A 2024 Seasonal Study of Key Fluvial-Lacustrine Zones

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Sediment geochemical dynamics in the Danube Delta exhibit spatial heterogeneity between bifurcations and lacustrine environments. Distinguishing whether trace metal enrichment stems from anthropogenic pollution or natural geogenic backgrounds is essential for environmental management. This 2024 study evaluates these dynamics across key bifurcations and the Rusca-Gorgova-Uzlina system during contrasting hydrological periods.

We assessed the geochemical status of riverbed and lakebed sediments, characterized carbonate and TOC distributions, quantified toxic and technophilic metals, and distinguished geogenic enrichment from anthropogenic contamination to provide valuable insights for the Biosphere Reserve's sustainable management.

Surface sediments were sampled during low-water (September 2024) and high-water (October 2024, post-flood) conditions. Analysis involved titration for CaCO₃ and TOC (Walkley-Black), ED-XRF for major and trace elements (Fe, Mn, Ti, As, Cr, Cu, Ni, Pb, Rb, Sr, V, Zn, Zr), and AAS for Hg. Results were compared against regulatory limits.

Riverbed sediments were predominantly non-carbonate (<10% CaCO₃, <1% TOC), reflecting high-energy conditions. Lakebed sediments showed higher accumulation (up to 35% CaCO₃, 7% TOC) from low-energy deposition. Most toxic metals (As, Pb, Zn) remained below regulatory thresholds. Notably, Cr, Cu, and Ni exceedances were linked to natural geogenic backgrounds rather than human impact. Isolated Hg elevations occurred during low-water, while Sr, Ti, and Zr patterns were driven by hydrodynamic sorting and mineralogical provenance.

The overall chemical status is acceptable; episodic exceedances do not indicate systemic pollution. Geochemical variability is driven by hydrodynamic processes and natural mineralogy rather than anthropogenic pressure, emphasizing the need for regular monitoring to maintain ecological integrity.

Keywords: Danube Delta; Environmental Monitoring; Fluvial-Lacustrine Transition; Seasonal Variability; Sediment Geochemistry; Trace Elements

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Patterns of Mercury Speciation in Pontic Shad (**Alosa immaculata**) at the Danube-Black Sea Interface

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Mercury pollution in aquatic ecosystems remains a global concern due to its toxicity and bio-magnification, particularly as methylmercury threatens wildlife and human fish consumers. The Danube-Black Sea interface is a critical but understudied zone where conditions may favor mercury accumulation and transformation. This study investigates mercury bioaccumulation in the migratory Pontic shad (*Alosa immaculata*), an ecologically and economically important regional species.

This study examined the biogeochemical distribution of total mercury and methylmercury in Pontic shad at the Danube-Black Sea interface and evaluated associated consumer health risks. Owing to its migratory behavior and commercial relevance, the species also serves as an effective sentinel for monitoring mercury contamination and pollutant transfer across the Danube-Black Sea continuum.

Pontic shad were collected during the late spring 2024 spawning migration from the Sfântu Gheorghe branch of the Danube-Black Sea interface. Freeze-dried muscle samples were analyzed for total mercury (THg) and methylmercury (MeHg) using direct mercury analysis (DMA-80, Milestone) following EPA Method 7473 and selective extraction protocols. Analytical quality was ensured using certified reference material (SRM 1566b).

Total mercury levels in *A. immaculata* showed relatively low variability and increased consistently with fish size, supporting the pattern of size-dependent bioaccumulation. All measured concentrations remained within European regulatory thresholds, indicating compliance with food safety standards. In contrast, methylmercury exhibited greater variability and was not related to fish size, suggesting that its distribution is influenced more by short-term and spatially variable environmental and dietary conditions in the Danube-Black Sea transition zone.

This study assessed total mercury and methylmercury in Pontic shad from the Sfântu Gheorghe area. Concentrations remained below EU safety limits, while variability in methylmercury suggested strong environmental influence. Overall, *A. immaculata* proved to be a suitable sentinel species for mercury monitoring at the Danube-Black Sea interface.

Keywords: Mercury; Methylmercury; **Alosa immaculata**

This work was supported by the MARBEFES (MARine Biodiversity and Ecosystem Functioning leading to Ecosystem Services) project under the European Union's Horizon Europe programme (Grant Agreement No. 101060937), as well as by the national projects PN23300103 and PN23300102 focused on Black Sea ecosystem monitoring and pollution assessment.

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Butyrylcholinesterase Biosensor for Guanitoxin Screening in Cyanobacterial Blooms

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The degradation and disruption of aquatic ecosystems induce the emergence of numerous phenomena with negative effects or the exacerbation of natural processes such as harmful algal blooms that are difficult to predict and manage. Cyanobacteria are important contributors to massive blooms and producers of various potent toxins including neurotic guanitoxin. Cholinesterase biosensors are a valuable tool for environmental screening and fast identification of contaminated samples.

Rational design of enzymatic biosensors for guanitoxin detection in environmental samples to improve the measurement sensitivity based on the differences between enzymes and optimization of kinetic working conditions.

Cyanobacterial strains were selected, cultivated and morphological characterized and compared with published descriptions of potentially guanitoxin-producing taxa. Boltz-1, an open-source AI model, was used for the in-silico study of enzyme-inhibitor biomolecular interactions. Biological samples treatment before analysis by freeze-taw and cell disruption was tested. Enzyme inhibition assays were carried out with both spectrometric and amperometric measurements.

Minimum sample treatment is optimum to reduce guanitoxin loss. BChE has a slighter higher affinity for guanitoxin in comparison with the AChE usually used for biosensor development. The inhibition is competitive and substrate concentration has important biosensor performances.

The optimized biosensor showed high operational stability, good reproducibility, and minimal interference in complex biological matrices, confirming its suitability for environmental monitoring.

Keywords: Harmful Algal Blooms; Butyrylcholinesterase Biosensor; Guanitoxin

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Compostable Polylactic Acid-Based Filter Cartridges for Point-of-Use Systems

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Water is the planet's most abundant and essential resource, yet freshwater availability remains unevenly distributed across regions. Studies have long warned that arid zones will continue to expand, while other regions will increasingly face severe flooding caused by intense rainfall events [1]. These developments are alarming because stronger rainfalls transport micropollutants from the atmosphere and soil into water bodies, disrupting the natural balance and reducing freshwater quality. To ensure access to safe drinking water in remote areas lacking centralized treatment infrastructure, particularly in underdeveloped countries or regions affected by hydro-climatic disasters such as floods, point-of-use (POU) systems for water purification and desalination have emerged as practical emergency solutions [2]. Although such technologies are already available, their widespread adoption is limited by high costs and the environmental impact of filter materials, especially where recycling systems are poorly implemented [3]. Consequently, both developed and developing countries increasingly require sustainable POU technologies aligned with circular bioeconomy principles targeting zero waste and zero carbon footprint objectives [4].

Development of biodegradable/compostable cartridge prototypes that are easy to integrate in the production line of filters manufacturers for water purification. In this respect, biocomposites based on poly(lactic acid) (PLA) were prepared, characterized, extruded in filaments and 3D printed.

The prototype was designed using free CAD software and prepared for 3D printing using the Orca Slicer Ink application on Creality Ender CR-10 Max printer. The tensile mechanical properties of the PLA-based biocomposite were determined according to ISO 527, mechanical analysis by DMA, and Charpy impact strength according to ISO 179. The PLA-based biocomposite filament was obtained by extrusion using a twin-screw extruder (DSE 20 Brabender).

The use of reinforcing agents, led to an increase in all mechanical properties. The tensile strength increased by 31%, the Young's modulus by 22% and the impact strength by 3%. The optimum recipe was further used for preparing the filament for 3D printing. Further on, the two filter prototypes - one based on commercial PLA (reference) and one on PLA-based biocomposite were tested to withstand the pressure of water in the Point-of-Use systems.

The PLA-based biocomposite selected as optimal in terms of thermal and mechanical properties was processed by specific melt processing methods to obtain filament for 3D printing (melt mixing and extrusion). The resulting 3D printed prototype has successfully passed the pressure test. Thus, the objective of the work was attained - the filter it is made of raw materials from renewable resources, it has improved mechanical and thermal properties and, as a result, can be used to obtain a housing model for water filters.

Keywords: PLA-Biocomposite; Filter Design; 3D-Printing

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Semi-Interpenetrating Polymer Sponge-Like Networks Based on Chitosan and Organosilanes for Metal Ion Retention

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The access to clean water is increasingly threatened by chemical pollutants, pathogens, and persistent heavy metals such as lead, cadmium, mercury, and copper, which accumulate in organisms and pose serious risks to human health and the environment. As global contamination intensifies, the demand for efficient, sustainable purification technologies has become critical. Recent research highlights natural-polymer-based materials-including chitosan, alginate, and related biopolymers-as promising solutions due to their high adsorption capacity, biodegradability, and low environmental impact, offering an effective approach to mitigating heavy-metal pollution [1-2]. Chitosan has a major advantage over other materials due to its exceptional capacity to generate hydrogels/cryogels/xerogels in various forms, including foams, which combined with accessible methods for producing artificial silicate networks, may represent a step forward for producing advanced materials for heavy metal ions decontamination of polluted water bodies [3-5].

Combining the benefits of using biopolymers, such as chitosan, with organosilanes, produced by sol-gel, for developing semi-interpenetrating polymer sponge-like networks with outstanding properties for metal ion retention in water.

For preparing the semi-interpenetrated network (semi-IPN) foams, commercial chitosan (CC) and two organosilane monomers were used. Three series of semi-interpenetrated foams with various ratios of chitosan were prepared and characterized using several analytical techniques-including FTIR, TGA, SEM and swelling-capacity measurements. XRF was used to evaluate the capacity of materials to uptake metal ions from various synthetic aqueous solutions.

Swelling degrees (SDs) were evaluated at different pH values to assess the stability of the semi-IPNs under different environmental conditions. The FTIR spectra confirmed the formation of silanol bonds and the successful incorporation of chitosan in all semi-IPNs, while TGA provided insight into their thermal stability. SEM micrographs revealed homogeneous morphologies and well-defined porous networks. Whereas, XRF analysis offered essential information regarding the metal ion retention capacity of the materials for Cu, Cd and Ag ions.

New chitosan-silicate semi-IPN sponges were developed, exhibiting superior structural, thermal, and morphological features to other related cryo-structures developed previously. Their swelling behavior and retention capacity were satisfying, indicating strong potential for future use as adsorbents in water purification processes.

Keywords: Chitosan; Organosilane; Sponge; Metal Ions

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The background features a soft, light blue and white illustration of a landscape. In the upper left, a large, pale sun is visible. To the right, there are stylized mountains and a rain cloud with dashed lines representing rain. A winding river flows through the center, and a dashed path with arrows and small circular markers winds across the scene, suggesting a journey or a process.

Priority 04 - Climate Change

Invasive Alien Species Observatory and Network Development for the Assessment of Climate Change Impacts and Contextual Ecosystem Services Evaluation in Black Sea Deltaic: IASON+, BSB00174

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Invasive alien species (IAS) have become an important driver of biodiversity change and exert severe pressure on natural ecosystems. The development of modelling approaches to assess and predict their distributions and impacts, and evaluate management options has increased substantially. At species/population level, most of the studies reported negative impacts; while at multi-species/ecosystem level, negative and both negative and positive impacts were similarly represented. It is important the development of the models to assess different impacts of IAS populations and highlight the need to advance their capabilities to predict future impacts at the Black Sea Bioregion. Further development of models that allow capturing the arrival, establishment and spread of IAS and assess their impacts in an integrated way is still needed. Spatial-temporal modelling techniques bridging with novel analytical capabilities may be the key for future achievement.

On the other hand, Ecosystem Services (ES) are the benefits that people obtain from ecosystems. These include provisioning services such as food and water; regulating services such as flood and disease control; cultural services such as spiritual, recreational, and cultural benefits; and supporting services such as nutrient cycling that maintaining the equilibrium conditions for the studied ecosystems. However, natural ecosystems are being degraded and destroyed at an unprecedented scale for Black Sea Bioregion, which poses a threat to the provision of these essential services.

One of the common territorial challenges in maintaining ES is the need for effective management and conservation of natural resources. This requires an integrated approach that takes into account the complex interactions between different ecosystems and the multiple benefits they provide. At the decision-making level, high-level science-policy platforms have been established to serve policy makers with integrated and agreed information on the extent of biodiversity and ecosystem loss and also present projections to the future. This information can be used to develop effective conservation and restoration strategies.

Keywords: Invasive Alien Species; Ecosystem Services; Climate Change

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Wildfires in the Danube Delta Biosphere Reserve: Satellite-Based Burned Area Mapping and Wildlife Habitat Impact Assessment

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Wetland fires are a recurring disturbance in European protected areas, with significant consequences for biodiversity and ecosystem functioning. The Danube Delta Biosphere Reserve, one of Europe's largest and most ecologically sensitive wetlands, experiences annual reed fires whose spatial extent and ecological impact remain insufficiently quantified. This study aims (1) to model active fire events in the Danube Delta, using a clustering algorithm based on VIIRS data; (2) determine burned areas through estimations based on active fires and Sentinel-2 imagery; (3) analyse fire spread patterns in relation to habitat types and seasonality; (4) assess the ecological impact of fires on protected wildlife habitats and fauna. The methodology offers a transferable framework for ecological fire impact assessment in other European wetland systems.

Keywords: Wetland Fires; Sentinel-2 Imagery; Burned Area Mapping

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On the Hydroclimatic Variability in the Lower Danube Basin

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Knowledge of the evolution of the discharge (Q) in the Lower Danube Basin (LDB) has proven to be an imperative requirement for the modern era from multiple socio-economic points of view.

Current means of investigation provide new specific tools that can be used to elucidate previously unexplored aspects. Since the Q evolution in the LDB is difficult to capture through expensive deterministic models, the present study uses stochastic modeling.

First, the distribution of precipitation over the entire Danube Basin (DB) is analyzed, which in turn is caused by atmospheric factors, the one analyzed extensively so far, such as the North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO), as well as the new one called the Greenland-Balkan Oscillation (GBO) [1]. The two factors represented by the corresponding indices NAOI and GBOI are complementary and capture by definition the latitudinal and, respectively, meridional atmospheric movements.

Testing them as predictors in predicting precipitation over the entire Danube Basin, as well as the discharge in the LDB, was the main objective.

We also propose a modeling of extreme events through Generalized Extreme Values (GEV) [2] of precipitation and maximum monthly discharge in the spring and summer seasons, to see if there is a single (stable) or multiple catchment basins, as well as the "rarity" of hazardous events (drought/flood periods). As an immediate objective, we test the existence of climate change in precipitation/discharge by including the mentioned climate indices as covariates in the GEV modeling. Obtaining the return periods/levels, respectively, through the GEV distributions with and without covariates leads us to the evaluation of hazardous hydrological phenomena in the LDB with the associated risk assessment.

Monthly and seasonal precipitation was obtained from daily precipitation of European Climate Assessment & Dataset (ECA&D). The first principal component (PC1) from the development by Empirical Orthogonal Functions (EOFs) of the precipitation ensemble in the DB was considered representative.

To highlight the distribution in the time-frequency domain and the coherence of the analyzed phenomena evolution, classical statistical methods, applications of information theory as mutual information and wavelet analysis were applied.

The return period (of the corresponding level) which is a key function for the transformation of hazard into damage through the impact function of the event, was analyzed.

For the prediction of the precipitation and discharge in LDB, recent deep learning (DP) method from neural network was applied to estimate them on independent data. The result of the investigation was obtained through a ridge-regression equation.

From the GEV analysis of the maximum monthly discharge in the spring season at Orsova, by introducing the GBO and NAO climate indices as covariates, the most statistically significant results were obtained by considering the GBOI in the winter and spring seasons.

The most important implications remain the estimates of the impact function in the assessment of flood/drought risk, estimates that assume the existence of intrinsic subjective factors (in the absence of prior notification of the danger).

Keywords: Danube Discharge; Climate Indices; Extreme Events

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Large-Scale Climate Variability Modes and Lower Danube Discharge

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The Danube River, the second longest river in Europe, plays a critical role in water resources, ecosystems, navigation, and socio-economic activities across its basin. Variations in the discharge are influenced by climatic conditions, particularly by the large-scale atmospheric circulation patterns operating on seasonal to multi-decadal timescales.

The research aims to provide a more accurate assessment of the relationship between large-scale climate variability modes and Danube discharge, and their influence on hydrological variability. The main objective of the study is to investigate the relationship between large-scale climate variability modes and the discharge in the Lower Danube Basin, both by analyzing temporal variability of the Lower Danube discharge and then by identifying the dominant large-scale climate variability modes impacting the region, and by assessing the link between climate variability indices and river discharge.

The analysis is given by using annual means data from four gauges along the Danube river, on the Romanian territory, namely, Orsova, Ceatal, Sulina, and Sf. Gheorghe, and from certain weather stations in the Lower Danube Basin. Large scale climate variability modes are described by means of climate indices related to the circulation atmospheric patterns (NAO, GBO and AMO).

The data were analyzed firstly by means of the Hodrick and Prescott (HP) filtering that separates them into a trend component and a cyclical component. The cyclic component stands for the inter-annual and decadal variations. Further the trend has been decomposed in turn, by means of Butterworth filtering, in constituents at the multi-decadal timescales (20-35 years, 60-80 years). The link between climate indices and river discharge was tested by cross-correlation analysis.

The inter-annual, decadal and multi-decadal variability of hydroclimatic parameters, assessed by appropriate methods, has revealed the presence of several short period variations (2-7 years), associated to atmospheric phenomena (NAO, GBO), decadal variations with a period of about 11 years and variations with longer periods, 22 and 40 years, associated both with Atlantic multi-decadal variability and possible with solar variability at solar cycle timescales. The cross-correlation analysis reveals significant relationships between large-scale climate variability modes and Danube River discharge in the Lower Danube Basin, with almost no lag between hydroclimatic parameters and climate indices at decadal timescales, and with a lag time of ~7-8 years, at multi-decadal timescales. The results highlight that low-frequency climate variability plays an important role in modulating discharge, the variations being most pronounced at decadal and multi-decadal scales, suggesting a delayed and integrated hydrological response to climate forcing.

This study demonstrates that large-scale climate variability modes exert a significant control on Danube River discharge in the Lower Danube Basin. The shown relationships between climate indices and discharge anomalies highlight the importance of atmospheric-oceanic circulation patterns in shaping hydrological variability across inter-annual, decadal and multi-decadal time scales.

Keywords: Lower Danube Discharge; Climate Indices; Inter-Annual, Decadal and Multi-Decadal Variability

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Nature-Based Solutions for Urban Runoff Treatment: Pilot-Scale Filtration System Assessment

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Urban water resources are under increasing pressure from both point and non-point source pollution, which collectively degrade the quality of receiving water bodies and pose risks to aquatic ecosystems. In urban environments, pollutants accumulate on impervious surfaces during dry periods and are mobilized into receiving waters primarily through stormwater runoff during rainfall events. This process is particularly critical during the first flush phenomenon, wherein the initial fraction of runoff carries the highest concentrations of accumulated pollutants, including nutrients, heavy metals, and Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs). Wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) have increasingly demonstrated limitations in managing both point-source and non-point source pollution under the growing pressures of urbanization and climate change. Nature-based solutions (NbS) offer sustainable alternatives by working with natural hydrological processes to enhance groundwater recharge through infiltration, attenuate flood risk, improve climate resilience, and achieve water quality improvement through pollutant retention and transformation.

This study investigates the performance of bioretention soil media employed in nature-based stormwater management systems such as bioswales, constructed wetlands, and rain gardens. A pilot-scale filtration system containing gravel with sand, as well as activated charcoal was used to treat both stormwater (street runoff) and rainwater (roof runoff) under experimental conditions.

The study pursued two principal objectives. The first was to determine water quality through physicochemical and microbiological analysis of urban stormwater and rainwater in Colentina area, Bucharest, to identify the pollutants present, and to assess the potential environmental risks associated with their discharge into receiving water bodies without treatment. The second objective was to evaluate the treatment performance and operational behaviour of a pilot-scale filtration system using different filter media. Comprehensive physicochemical and microbiological analyses enabled a systematic assessment of influent water quality and treatment efficiency across both runoff types and filter media.

Keywords: Nature-Based Solutions; Urban Runoff Treatment; Water Quality

Priority 05 - Extreme Events

Quantifying Drought Stress and Nature-Based Solution Effectiveness in a Degraded Danube Floodplain: A Field-Calibrated Water Balance Modelling Approach

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Degraded floodplain landscapes in southern Romania face a structural and deepening water deficit driven by rising atmospheric evaporative demand and highly variable precipitation. The former Danube floodplain at Maglavit and Cetate, disconnected from river dynamics since the 1970s, has lost the natural water retention mechanisms that once buffered against seasonal drought. The central question is how much water retention capacity Nature-based Solutions would need to restore to meaningfully reduce agricultural and ecological drought stress under current and future climates.

This study aimed to: (1) quantify the site water balance and characterise soil moisture dynamics from a 7-month field monitoring campaign; (2) calibrate and validate a daily root zone soil water balance model against observed soil moisture; (3) apply the model to a 33-year historical climate record to assess long-term drought stress patterns; and (4) evaluate NBS sensitivity by quantifying stress day reduction as a function of increased root zone water storage capacity across four climate scenarios.

Five soil moisture stations measuring volumetric water content at six depths (10 to 90 cm) and an automatic weather station were deployed at the site from June 2025. Reference ET₀ was computed using the FAO-56 Penman-Monteith equation and validated against a calibrated Hargreaves-Samani estimate. A single-layer bucket model was calibrated against observed root zone soil water storage using `scipy.optimize`, then driven by 33 years of daily climate data from Calafat station. Future scenarios followed a delta-change approach applied to EURO-CORDEX ensemble medians for RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 at two time horizons.

Summer 2025 recorded only 54 mm of precipitation against 619 mm of ET₀ demand, with a mean crop coefficient of 0.17 indicating severe vegetation water stress. The calibrated model achieved NSE = 0.916 against observed soil water storage. The 33-year hindcast revealed a mean of 19.3 annual stress days, with 52% of years recording zero stress, confirming episodic rather than chronic drought dynamics. Stress days are projected to increase to 28.5 under RCP4.5 2041-2070 and 46.6 under RCP8.5 2071-2100. A 30 mm increase in root zone storage capacity halves stress days under current climate (19.3 to 9.6) but yields diminishing returns under high-end warming, reducing stress by only 14 days per year by 2071-2100.

Southern Romania faces a structurally negative water balance that climate change will intensify, but the episodic nature of drought stress means that modest increases in root zone water retention can substantially reduce stress frequency under current conditions. The analysis provides a quantitative basis for NBS design, identifying shallow retention ponds, controlled floodplain reconnection and soil organic matter improvement as priority measures. The finding that NBS effectiveness declines under high warming underscores the importance of early implementation. The modelling framework, calibrated against field observations and extended over a 33-year record, is transferable to comparable degraded floodplain sites across the Danube basin.

Keywords: Water Balance Modelling; Soil Moisture Monitoring; Danube Floodplain

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Integrated Satellite and Drone Monitoring for Wildfire Prevention

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Romania faces an increasing threat from wildfires, driven largely by human activities such as uncontrolled agricultural burning and negligence, with over 8200 vegetation fires recorded in 2025. These fires devastate biodiversity by disrupting ecosystem balance, while also releasing carbon that exacerbates climate change.

To address this challenge, we propose an integrated platform called EcoGuardian that leverages satellite remote sensing and drone surveillance to identify and mitigate wildfire risks. First, we utilise satellite imagery to map areas of dry vegetation using the Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), which is a key indicator of vegetation health and dryness, in order to pinpoint potential wildfire hotspots and the Normalised Burn Ratio (NBR), which detects the areas most affected by wildfires. We also use the Normalised Difference Water Index (NDWI) to detect the nearest water sources in the event of a wildfire. A DJI Mini 4 Pro drone is deployed to survey these high-risk areas, capturing aerial video of the ground conditions. The video feed is processed on a server, extracting frames for analysis. We employ Meta's Segment Anything Model 2 (SAM2) to automatically segment and two computer vision models to identify fire-prone elements in the imagery, such as dry vegetation or litter (e.g. glass and plastic bottles) that could ignite or fuel fires.

The identified risks are then geotagged and visualised on a web-based map platform. Authorities can use this tool to see up-to-date dryness maps alongside flagged hazards at specific GPS coordinates, enabling targeted preventive action (such as clearing debris or issuing warnings) in areas prone to human-induced fires. The initial use case is the deployment of a drone to gather the necessary data in a dry-vegetation area near Timisoara to validate its effectiveness. Our approach wants to demonstrate how emerging technologies, such as Earth observation and image segmentation, can converge to preserve ecosystem biodiversity. Taking preventive actions before the fire starts, the solution helps safeguard natural habitats and also reduces carbon emissions from fires, contributing to climate change mitigation. While developed in a Romanian context, this method is scalable globally for proactive wildfire risk management.

Keywords: Wildfire Prevention; Drone Surveillance; Satellite Imagery; NDVI; SAM2; Environmental Monitoring

Modeling the Rain Runoff Process in Order to Obtain an Optimal Distribution of NbSs' in an Urban District of Bucharest

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Urbanization alters the urban water balance by increasing impervious surfaces, reducing infiltration, and accelerating surface runoff, thereby increasing pressure on urban drainage systems and flood vulnerability during intense rainfall events. Nature-based solutions (NbS) are increasingly recognized for their potential to restore infiltration processes and support decentralized stormwater management in highly urbanized environments.

This study investigates the hydrological effects of land-use change and NbS implementation within a 12 km² urban catchment in Sector 2, Bucharest, Romania. The objective is to assess and compare the impacts of different urban development scenarios on runoff generation, infiltration, and sewer network loading.

Three urban development scenarios were comparatively assessed: (i) the current urban condition, (ii) conversion of 69% of industrial surfaces into leisure areas with moderately increased permeability, and (iii) systematic implementation of NbS measures, including local runoff retention, infiltration enhancement, and local water reuse. Hydrological simulations were conducted using Watershed Modeling System (WMS) and Storm Water Management Model (SWMM) to quantify changes in runoff, infiltration, and sewer network loading.

The results indicate that land-use modification alone has limited hydrological influence. Scenario (ii) produced only minor system changes, with infiltration increasing by approximately 5% and sewer-related flows decreasing by less than 1%, suggesting that moderate permeability improvements are insufficient to substantially alter runoff generation processes in highly urbanized catchments. In contrast, Scenario (iii) produced a significant redistribution of the urban water balance. Total infiltration increased from approximately 33 l/s under baseline conditions to 55-59 l/s, corresponding to a 67-81% increase, while sewer inflow decreased from approximately 196 l/s to 138-169 l/s.

The findings demonstrate that the effectiveness of urban interventions depends primarily on restoring infiltration and decentralized stormwater retention processes rather than solely modifying land use. Integrating NbS into urban planning can substantially reduce hydraulic stress on sewer systems and improve urban flood resilience under increasing urbanization and climate pressures. The proposed approach provides practical support for sustainable stormwater management and climate adaptation strategies in urban environments.

Keywords: Urban Runoff; Runoff Modelling; Stormwater Management

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Natural Events in Romania Becoming Extreme: Scientific Investigations to Reduce Their Impact

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Romania faces a combination of high hazard exposure and high structural vulnerability, where natural events frequently escalate into societal disasters. Major earthquakes, recurrent floods, severe droughts, and landslides intersect with fragile infrastructure, institutional weaknesses, and social inequality, allowing even moderate events to produce disproportionate impacts comparable to extreme ones. The efforts of the scientific community and public authorities aim to prevent natural hazards from escalating into societal disasters.

In this context, the study outlines research methods developed by the researchers of the Institute of Geodynamics, who contribute to these initiatives by applying geophysical techniques and analytical investigations of key parameters associated with earthquakes and landslides.

This study applies Romanian case-studies using medium-term prediction methods for earthquakes and landslides. Seismic precursors are identified through earthquake-catalog analysis and geomagnetic-electromagnetic monitoring of pre-seismic anomalies. Landslide assessment employs Direct Current Resistivity to detect subsurface conductivity variations linked to moisture, weak layers, and potential slip surfaces.

Intermediate-depth earthquakes in the Vrancea zone, with 4-5 major events per century ($M_w \geq 6.9$), pose a major threat to the country. Analysing the earthquake and focal mechanism catalogs, two reverse-fault types of subcrustal earthquakes were put in evidence: events with a SW-NE striking fault plane (1940, 1977, 1986, 1990) and events with a NW-SE striking fault plane, both contributing to regional hazard. Additional, some NW-SE striking fault plane seismic events ($4.8 \leq m_b \leq 5.1$) cluster at >160 km depth and precede major earthquakes at 90-133 km depth by 3-4 years, being a possible seismic precursor. The geomagnetic methodology developed by Dumitru Stanica detected pre-seismic electromagnetic anomalies and has demonstrated ~ 48 -hour lead times, enabling preventive institutional protocols. Another type of geophysical methods for assessing geological hazards are geoelectrical investigations (VES-vertical electrical sounding), which, applied on the landslides (e.g., at Ratesti Monastery), identify rupture planes, active faults, and unstable clay layers.

Findings from Vrancea subcrustal seismicity and slope-instability assessments in specific zones highlight a systemic regional threat that requires integrated monitoring to protect communities. The methods presented in the study prove to be an important constituent part of the monitoring and prevention activities aimed at mitigating their impact.

Keywords: Earthquakes; Landslides; Prediction; Geoelectrical Investigations; Geomagnetism
The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Enhancing Flood Susceptibility Mapping Through High-Resolution Earth Observation: A Data-Driven Comparative Analysis

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Flood susceptibility maps are essential tools for identifying high-risk areas, enabling disaster management authorities to make informed decisions, allocate resources efficiently, and implement appropriate mitigation measures. However, traditional flood forecasting methods often face limitations in spatial resolution and adaptability under changing climatic conditions, particularly in data-scarce regions where limited observational data further constrain model reliability and accuracy. The lack of high-quality and spatially continuous datasets remains a major challenge for effective flood susceptibility assessment in such areas.

This study addresses these gaps by applying a data-driven geospatial approach that integrates high-resolution Earth Observation and GIS data to improve flood susceptibility assessment in a small river basin in Romania.

This approach is based on ten flood conditioning factors, including Elevation, Slope, Topographic Wetness Index (TWI), Topographic Position Index (TPI), Profile Curvature, Aspect, Soil Texture, Distance to the River, Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) and Soil Moisture. Historical flood extent data extracted from PlanetScope imagery were used for model training and validation. Two statistical methods, Frequency Ratio (FR) and Weight of Evidence (WoE), were applied to evaluate spatial flood susceptibility patterns at a 12.5 m resolution.

Results indicate that both models successfully capture spatial variability of flood-prone areas. Approximately 50% of the basin exhibits low to very low flood susceptibility, while high and very high susceptibility covers about 17-20% and 8-9% of the basin, respectively. High-risk areas are mainly situated along river corridors in the central and southern basin, overlapping with built-up areas; consequently, about 38% (WoE) and 30% (FR) of the total built-up area falls within high and very high susceptibility classes. Model performance assessment based on the area under the curve (AUC) shows that WoE (0.944) outperforms FR (0.881) in predictive accuracy, while FR tends to underestimate flood-prone areas.

These findings highlight the effectiveness of integrating high-resolution open-source Earth Observation data with statistical modelling approaches for flood susceptibility mapping. The proposed framework provides a reliable and transferable tool for identifying flood-prone areas, supporting effective disaster management and planning in data-scarce regions under changing climatic conditions.

Keywords: Flood Susceptibility Mapping; GIS; Data-Driven Modelling; Remote Sensing; High-Resolution

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Geophysical Investigation in Archaeological Sites

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In the area of archaeological interest located in the vicinity of Morii Lake, direct current geoelectric measurement were carried out, executing Vertical Electric Surveys (VES). In order to obtain optimal information on the position and depth of possible buried structures, the version of the Schlumberger device was used. The obtained data were stored in a database, then apparent resistivity values were calculated and the resistivity sections for the $AB/2$ depth were obtained.

Four geoelectric profiles parallel to each other with lengths of 50 m each were made, the distance between the profiles being 5 m and resulting in a studied perimeter of approximately 750 square m, the orientation of the profiles being S-N.

The distances between the measuring electrodes MN was 1 m and the maximum distance between the current injection electrodes (AB) was 8 m. The resistivity sections resulting from data processing show an image of the apparent resistivity distribution in the depth range $AB/2 = 4$ m, and the distance between the VES was 5 m.

The geoelectric measurements highlighted the apparent resistivity contrasts, providing information about possible buried structures in the 0,5 - 2 m depth interval. On the apparent resistivity section obtained from VES measurements, there are significant apparent resistivity contrast between the buried structures and the geological environment, highlighting the encountered lithological changes. The obtained results illustrate the usefulness of the geoelectric method in outlining the buried structures. The interpretation of the data obtained through VES type geoelectrical measurements provides us with information on the lithological composition of the rock in area of interest.

Keywords: VES; Profiles; Resistivity; Archaeological

Nature-Based Solutions for Urban Stormwater Management: Enhancing Urban Resilience Through Smart and Sustainable Planning: A Case Study in Bucharest

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Urban areas are increasingly exposed to extreme rainfall events, placing significant pressure on conventional sewer systems and amplifying flood risks. In this context, nature-based solutions (NBS) have emerged as a promising approach to enhance urban water system resilience by promoting local retention, infiltration, and reuse of stormwater. This study assesses the hydrological and economic performance of a proposed NBSs' distribution within a 12 km² urban catchment in the Tei area of Bucharest, characterized by heterogeneous land use and varying degrees of imperviousness.

A hydrological modelling framework was applied to compare three scenarios: (i) baseline conditions with no intervention, (ii) land-use transformation towards leisure areas with moderate increases in permeability, and (iii) systematic integration of NBSs' and alternative water resources (AWR), including runoff capture, infiltration, and decentralized reuse. Results indicate that the NBSs' scenario reduces the annual volume of water entering the sewer system by approximately 840,000 m³, while significantly increasing infiltration. In contrast, the leisure-based scenario yields only marginal hydrological improvements, with a reduction of approximately 48,000 m³/year.

From an economic perspective, the reduction in conveyed stormwater translates into estimated operational savings ranging between EUR84,000 and EUR210,000 per year, associated with decreased pumping, transport, and system loading. These findings demonstrate that NBS can effectively shift stormwater management from a conveyance-based paradigm towards a decentralized and resource-oriented approach.

The results highlight that the effectiveness of NBSs' is strongly dependent on local physical and urban conditions, requiring integration into spatial planning and policy frameworks. Beyond hydrological performance, the study underscores the role of NBS as a strategic instrument for improving urban resilience to extreme events, while contributing to the sustainable management of water resources within the broader Danube-Black Sea system.

Keywords: Nature-Based Solutions; Urban Stormwater; Urban Planning; Hydrological Modelling; Urban Resilience; Cost-Benefit Analysis

**Priority 06 - Ecosystems and
Biodiversity**

Genetic Diversity Assessment of Aquatic Macroinvertebrates from a Biodiversity Hotspot in Romania

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Aquatic macroinvertebrates are widely used as bioindicators of freshwater ecosystem integrity. However, species-level identification, particularly of morphologically cryptic larvae, remains challenging. Developing regional DNA barcode reference libraries is therefore essential for improving ecological assessments in regions with high species richness and endemism.

This study aimed to: (1) generate a comprehensive mtCOI barcode dataset from freshwater macroinvertebrates collected in the Romanian Carpathians, (2) evaluate genetic divergence patterns among taxa, and (3) assess the effectiveness of DNA barcoding for species-level identification of immature stages.

A total of 2,117 specimens representing larval, pupal, and adult stages were collected from headwaters and lowland rivers. We generated 1,567 COI barcode sequences corresponding to 328 morphospecies, 204 genera, 94 families, and 17 orders. Sequence analyses included BIN assignment through BOLD, K2P genetic distance calculations, and Maximum Likelihood phylogenetic reconstruction.

The dataset recovered 453 OTUs, most showing strong correspondence with recognized species boundaries. Genetic divergence analyses revealed clear separation between intra- and interspecific variation while highlighting substantial cryptic diversity, particularly in headwater ecosystems. The study added numerous novel BINs to BOLD, many lacking previous species-level assignments. DNA barcoding enabled reliable identification of many larval specimens that could not be identified morphologically.

Our results demonstrate the strong potential of COI barcoding for improving freshwater biomonitoring and resolving taxonomic uncertainty in aquatic macroinvertebrates. Expanding curated regional barcode libraries will strengthen ecological assessment frameworks and may support future large-scale applications in connected river systems, including the Danube basin. Continued efforts are needed to address remaining taxonomic gaps for endemic and poorly represented taxa.

Keywords: Species-Level Identification; DNA Reference Data; mtCOI Barcoding

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Linking Environmental Heterogeneity to Freshwater Microbial Community Assembly

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Aquatic microbial communities are essential drivers of nutrient cycling and ecosystem functioning, yet the environmental factors shaping their spatial distribution in freshwater ecosystems remain insufficiently understood. Lakes connected to major river-sea continuums, such as Lake Razim, represent dynamic environments where physico-chemical gradients may differentially influence microbial assemblages in water and sediments.

Microbial community composition was evaluated in water and sediment samples collected from five representative sites using 16S rRNA metabarcoding analysis. Community structure and diversity were analyzed in relation to key environmental variables and ecological indices, including Shannon and Simpson diversity metrics.

Sediment microbial communities showed higher diversity and greater structural stability than water column communities. Proteobacteria and Ignavibacteriae were dominant in sediments, whereas Bacteroidetes, Planctomycetes, and Verrucomicrobia were more abundant in the water column. Increased abundance of Bacteroidetes was associated with elevated concentrations of total and water-soluble organic carbon, suggesting a relationship between carbon availability and heterotrophic microbial taxa. Overall, environmental gradients were linked to distinct compartment-specific microbial assemblages across the lake ecosystem.

This study provides an integrated perspective on microbial distribution patterns within a freshwater ecosystem and demonstrates the importance of environmental gradients in structuring aquatic microbiomes. The findings also emphasize the continuing gaps in understanding the ecological and functional roles of specific microorganisms in aquatic environments.

Keywords: Metabarcoding; 16S rRNA; Freshwater

Integrated Benthic Assessment of ROSCI0066 Danube Delta - Marine Area: Habitats, Biodiversity, and Conservation Implications for the Romanian Black Sea

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Benthic habitats and macrozoobenthic communities are essential for marine biodiversity, ecosystem functioning, and resilience. Despite their ecological importance, baseline data on benthic community structure and habitat condition within the 20-40 m depth zone of the Romanian Black Sea remain scarce. In the context of increasing anthropogenic pressures, GeoEcoMar conducted a long-term investigation of benthic habitats in this depth zone within the Natura 2000 site ROSCI0066 "Danube Delta - Marine Area" to provide scientific support for ecosystem-based management.

This study aimed to characterize benthic habitat distribution, assess macrozoobenthic community structure, and evaluate ecosystem resilience within the 20-40 m depth zone of ROSCI0066, in order to inform conservation planning and MSFD-compliant management.

Over 18 field campaigns (2015-2025), 246 sampling stations were investigated. Sediment classification followed the Folk 5/7 system, aligned with EMODnet Seabed Habitats and national schemes. Habitat distribution maps, developed by integrating sediment types, depth, and coordinates within a GIS framework, were validated using multibeam bathymetry and Side-Scan Sonar. Macrozoobenthic samples were collected using a Van Veen grab (one replicate per station, consistent with regional monitoring protocols). Habitat classification followed the MSFD typology and Natura 2000 framework, while status and resilience were assessed via biodiversity and ecological quality indices.

A total of 146 macrozoobenthic species were identified, reflecting the considerable species richness of the Romanian continental shelf. Nine benthic habitat types were delineated according to MSFD classification, three corresponding to Natura 2000 categories. Spatial distribution patterns were heterogeneous, strongly associated with sediment characteristics and environmental gradients. Mapping delineated ecologically significant areas and zones exposed to cumulative anthropogenic pressures. Areas with higher species richness and complex benthic communities exhibited increased stability and resilience. While several habitats maintain a favorable ecological state, localized human activities threaten long-term functioning. Consequently, targeted management and conservation measures were proposed.

This integrated assessment provides crucial scientific support for marine spatial planning and Natura 2000 management. The findings deepen the understanding of ecosystem functioning, resilience, and vulnerability, directly supporting MSFD objectives and long-term biodiversity conservation strategies. The proposed conservation and management measures are expected to guide adaptive governance of ROSCI0066, contributing to the sustainable use and long-term protection of Romanian Black Sea benthic ecosystems.

Keywords: Marine Protected Area; Biodiversity Assessment; Habitat Mapping

This work was supported by the Romanian Ministry of Education and Research within the framework of the National CORE Programs (projects PN 23300202, PN23300101 and PN2330103), and by the Large Infrastructure Operational Programme through the project 'Revision of the Danube Delta Biosphere Reserve Management Plan and Regulation' (SMIS Code 123322, contract no. 253/18.06.2019).

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Exploring Psychrotolerant Bacterial Diversity across Antarctic Aquatic Microniches during the ROICE2026 Expedition

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Antarctic ecosystems are highly sensitive to climate-driven environmental changes, yet the culturable fraction of their microbial diversity remains underexplored (Cong et al., 2020). Distinct Antarctic microniches, including meltwater-associated environments and wildlife-influenced habitats (Morozova et al., 2022), may harbor specialized bacterial communities with ecological relevance and adaptive potential under extreme environmental conditions (Krucon et al., 2021). This study aimed to investigate the cultivable microbiota across different Antarctic aquatic microhabitats during the ROICE2026 Romanian expedition.

The study aimed to characterize culturable bacterial diversity across Antarctic aquatic microniches and compare microbial profiles from meltwater and fauna-influenced environments. Additionally, we sought to identify ecologically relevant temperature-based taxa using culture-dependent microbiological methods and MALDI-TOF mass spectrometry.

Samples were collected during the ROICE2026 expedition (January 24-February 14, 2026) from microhabitats near King Sejong Station (King George Island, Antarctica), including meltwater-associated aquatic environments and ASPA171-protected areas. Water samples were processed microbiologically using filtration and culture-based workflows, including selective cultivation on multiple media, incubation at 4C and 15C, colony purification, and preliminary taxonomic identification by MALDI-TOF MS.

Bacterial colonies with diverse morphologies and varying degrees of pigmentation were recovered under different culture conditions, and presumptive identification was achieved for about 50% of isolates. Distinct Antarctic microniches exhibited distinct culturable bacterial profiles, suggesting ecological structuring linked to local environmental heterogeneity. Repeated recovery of *Janthinobacterium lividum* across multiple environmental conditions and culture variants suggested strong ecological adaptability and metabolic versatility under polar stress. Meltwater-associated environments were dominated by psychrotolerant and psychrofilic Gammaproteobacteria, including multiple *Pseudomonas* species, whereas possible snow-associated microniches yielded taxa such as *Masilia*, *Arthrobacter*, and *Flavobacterium*. The occasional isolation of *Escherichia coli* from penguin-associated environments may reflect transient external contamination rather than a dominant native taxon.

Microenvironmental niches within Antarctic meltwater ecosystems harbor diverse psychrotolerant and ecologically specialized bacterial communities shaped by local environmental heterogeneity and extreme climatic conditions. The analyzed samples yielded a diverse cultivable fraction, dominated by Gram-negative bacteria, and the high percentage of strains unidentified by MALDI-TOF MS highlights the need to use complementary molecular methods capable of identifying new taxa. These findings support the value of culture-based approaches for exploring microbial diversity, ecological adaptation, and ecosystem functioning in polar environments.

Keywords: Psychrotolerant Bacteria; Polar Microniches; Antarctic Microbiota

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Mapping Illegal Fishing Events from News Media for Romanian Danube Basin

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Unreported and illicit fishing activities remain a significant obstacle to sustainable management of large freshwater ecosystems, especially in regions where official surveillance systems provide limited or inconsistent records. Across the Danube River basin and the Danube Delta, information regarding fisheries-related offenses is frequently documented only in regional and national media outlets, creating a dispersed and difficult-to-standardize information source. To address this limitation, we applied a computational event-reconstruction framework capable of extracting and linking illegal fishing incidents from Romanian-language online news reports. The approach combines language embeddings with automated identification of relevant contextual elements, including geographic references, fish taxa, fishing practices, confiscated materials, and institutional actors involved in enforcement actions. Similarities among articles are evaluated through a multi-criteria scoring system incorporating semantic correspondence, shared entities, geographical distance, and temporal association. Using a dataset of Romanian press publications spanning the period 2006-2026, the method successfully grouped related reports into coherent event structures distributed across space and time. The reconstructed patterns highlighted repeated concentrations of illegal fishing activity near protected zones and in sectors subject to intensified inspection efforts. The resulting geospatial database was subsequently integrated into a Google Earth Engine environment, offering a scalable resource for environmental crime assessment, spatial risk analysis, and fisheries governance support. Compare official data with news data and assess the difference.

Keywords: Illegal Fishing; Natural Language Processing; Graph-Based Analysis; Geospatial Analysis

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Success Mechanisms of Invasive Plant Species in the Danube Basin: Physiological Traits, Ecological Impact, and Their Role in Environmental Quality Monitoring

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The Danube Basin hosts a rapidly expanding assemblage of invasive plant species that significantly alter riparian, floodplain, and aquatic ecosystems. Their success is driven by a combination of functional traits, high ecological plasticity, and tolerance to environmental stressors. Despite their negative impacts, several invasive taxa also exhibit physiological and biochemical characteristics that make them potential bioindicators of environmental quality, particularly in systems affected by hydrological alteration and pollution.

This study aims to (1) identify the key physiological traits that underpin the invasion success of major vascular plant invaders in the Danube Basin, (2) evaluate their ecological impacts across terrestrial and aquatic habitats, and (3) assess their capacity to accumulate heavy metals and serve as indicators of soil and water quality.

We synthesized published data on photosynthetic performance, pigment composition, stress physiology, growth strategies, and metal accumulation for dominant invasive species across the upper, middle, and lower Danube sectors. Ecological impacts were evaluated based on documented effects on native vegetation, habitat structure, nutrient cycling, and ecosystem functioning.

Invasive species exhibit a suite of advantageous traits, including high photosynthetic efficiency (*Ailanthus altissima*), strong antioxidant responses (*Amorpha fruticosa*), rapid clonal expansion (*Reynoutria japonica*), and high growth rates under low light (*Elodea nuttallii*). Several taxa—such as *Ceratophyllum demersum*, *Amorpha fruticosa*, and *Reynoutria japonica*—accumulate substantial concentrations of Cd, Pb, Zn, and Cu, maintaining physiological performance even under contamination. Ecologically, these species reduce native biodiversity, alter habitat structure, and modify biogeochemical processes in riparian and aquatic systems.

The invasion success of Danube Basin plant invaders is strongly linked to their physiological plasticity, stress tolerance, and efficient resource use. Their capacity to accumulate heavy metals highlights their dual role as both ecosystem disruptors and potential bioindicators of environmental degradation.

Integrating physiological and ecological data provides a robust framework for monitoring invasive species dynamics and for developing targeted management strategies. The bioindicator potential of selected taxa offers new opportunities for assessing pollution and ecosystem health in the Danube Basin, supporting evidence-based conservation and restoration planning.

Keywords: Invasive Plant Species; Danube Basin; Physiological Traits; Ecological Impact; Environmental Monitoring; Heavy Metal Accumulation; Bioindicators; Stress Tolerance; Photosynthetic Performance; Riparian and Aquatic Ecosystems; Ecological Plasticity; Habitat Alteration; Ecosystem Functioning; Management Strategies

The Biodiversity, Ecological Status and Dynamics of the Benthic Community Along the Sfantu Gheorghe Branch, Danube Delta, between 2016 and 2025

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The Sfantu Gheorghe Branch is one of the most dynamic sectors of the Danube Delta, where natural hydrological variability, sediment redistribution and past hydrotechnical works have shaped a complex mosaic of lotic, lentic and transitional habitats. This study assesses the biodiversity, ecological status and temporal dynamics of the benthic community along the Sfantu Gheorghe Branch and its associated meanders, based on multiannual biological data collected between 2016 and 2025. Macrozoobenthic samples were collected from the main branch, rectified meanders, natural channels and adjacent lake sectors using a multi-habitat sampling approach adapted from national ecological monitoring methodologies. The analysis focused on taxonomic composition, abundance, frequency, mean density, dominant taxa and ecological significance, with results interpreted in relation to habitat type, substrate characteristics and hydrological connectivity. The results indicate pronounced spatial and temporal variability in benthic community structure. Earlier campaigns, particularly those from 2016-2017, showed very high benthic densities and a community dominated by Oligochaeta, Chironomidae, molluscs and crustaceans. Subsequent data from 2024 and 2025 revealed a more heterogeneous pattern, with marked differences among the main branch, meanders, channels and lakes. The highest diversity and densities were generally associated with habitats characterized by organic-rich sediments, submerged vegetation or shell-rich substrates, while more dynamic sectors of the main branch supported communities dominated by tolerant and eurytopic taxa. In 2025, Oligochaeta remained the dominant group, accompanied by Chironomidae, Nematoda, Corophiidae, Gammaridae and molluscs such as *Corbicula fluminea*, *Dreissena polymorpha* and *Lithoglyphus naticoides*. The occurrence of the polychaete *Laonome xeprovala* further highlights the relevance of invasive or expanding taxa in the ecological assessment of the area. The benthic community reflects a system strongly controlled by substrate type, hydrodynamic regime and organic matter availability. Although ecological status assessments based on family richness indicate good to very good conditions in several sectors, the dominance of tolerant taxa and the marked interannual fluctuations suggest the need for integrated, long-term monitoring of benthic biodiversity in the Danube Delta River-meander system.

Keywords: Benthic Fauna; Meanders; Sf. Gheorghe; Danube Delta; Biodiversity

The Role of Halophytes in Supporting Biodiversity of the Danube Delta-Black Sea System

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Provide Halophytes are salt-tolerant plants-such as *Salicornia* sp. and *Festuca* sp.-that thrive in highly saline environments. They act as foundational ecosystems, providing essential food, shelter, and soil stabilization for coastal and arid biodiversity while enabling long-term ecological restoration and carbon sequestration. Halophytes are thus recognized as a diverse group of vascular plants with a system of biochemical, morphological and physiological adaptations that enable them to overcome osmotic and ionic stresses or to increase their tolerance to such.

This work evaluates the potential applications of saline land vegetation, particularly halophytes, in climate change mitigation, phytoremediation, desalination, and saline agriculture, as well as in the production of food, medicine, nutraceuticals, and secondary metabolites. Maximizing the utility of these species is imperative for reclaiming saline soils, improving the livelihoods of resource-poor farmers, restoring ecological balance, and support biodiversity of the Danube Delta-Black Sea system.

This study aims to document and address critical knowledge gaps in halophyte research, specifically concerning the preservation of biodiversity within the Danube Delta-Black Sea ecosystem.

1. The Ecotone Stabilization & Buffer: Halophytic communities reduce hydrodynamic energy from the Black Sea, stabilizing coastlines due to their dense root networks

2. The Microhabitat Provision: The high stem succulence and salt excretion create microclimates that foster rich invertebrate and avian diversity.

3. The Biogeochemical and Desalination: Halophytes improve substrate quality, enabling the germination and persistence of less salt-tolerant species.

4. The Trophic Base and Detritus: Halophytic biomass serves as a fundamental base for the detrital food web.

A comprehensive and systematic literature search was performed across the Scopus, PubMed, and Web of Science databases. The evaluation was limited to peer-reviewed studies, original research articles, review papers, and books published from 2020 to the present; publications prior to this period were excluded because they lacked relevance to the core focus of this investigation - the halophytes and biodiversity. Furthermore, the selection criteria were restricted to English-language publications.

Hence halophytes hold great potential for ecological restoration and sustainable agriculture, we have attempted to document and address some of the critical gaps in halophyte research in sustaining biodiversity of the Danube Delta-Black Sea system:

1. Biodiversity-Soil Feedback Dynamics:
2. Climate Change and Sea Level Rise:
3. Invasive Species Proliferation:
4. Eutrophication and Water Quality Interactions:

So, the halophytes support the biodiversity of the Danube Delta-Black Sea system by acting as critical buffers, supplying organic matter, and providing microhabitats for specialized fauna. They mitigate the impacts of sea-level rise, fluctuating salinities, and coastal erosion. Areas near the Black Sea are affected by various amounts of tidal salt inflow and typically are dominated by halophytic (salt-loving) plants, such as glasswort (*Salicornia* sp) and alkaligrass (*Juncus* sp).

Halophytes (salt-tolerant plants making up less than 2% of global flora) are crucial for maintaining the ecological balance of arid, coastal, and salt-affected lands. They support regional biodiversity, rehabilitate degraded soils, and act as climate-resilient solutions for future agriculture and food security.

In same time, significant lacunae persist in the scientific understanding of halophytic vegetation dynamics within the Danube Delta-Black Sea system. In particular, empirical data are lacking

regarding how these salt-tolerant communities withstand the concurrent threats of accelerated sea-level rise, anthropogenic habitat fragmentation, and localized eutrophication.

Accelerating research into halophytic resources is imperative to support long-term resource security. Achieving this requires a coordinated approach: safeguarding endangered halophytes, curbing overexploitation, and implementing comprehensive regulatory frameworks to manage the trade-off between ecological conservation and sustainable economic utilization.

Keywords: Halophytes; Biodiversity; Danube Delta; Black Sea

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The background features a light blue and white abstract design. A prominent element is a winding, multi-lane river or road that flows from the top left towards the bottom right. In the upper left, a bridge with several vertical supports spans across a section of the river. To the right of the river, there is a complex network of thin, light blue lines connecting various circular nodes, some of which are highlighted in a darker blue. The overall aesthetic is clean, modern, and technological.

Priority 07 - Digital Twin

Monitoring and Logging Service for Natural Resources: New Trends and Challenges

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The modern digital infrastructures, based on network equipment, gateways, servers, virtualized services, and distributed components, availability and security directly depend on the ability of operators to observe in real time the status of systems and the events generated by them. The lack of a centralized monitoring and logging solution leads to difficulties detecting anomalies, delays in diagnosis, and the inability to correlate technical incidents with security events.

In the context of natural resources, a monitoring and logging service should be more than a dashboard that collects sensor values. The new trend is toward an integrated observability platform that combines sensors, environmental data, edge processing, cloud analytics, logs, metrics, traces, alerts, and decision-support services.

Therefore, implementing a unified monitoring and logging service addresses the need for continuous operational control, identification of communication degradations, supervision of access and configuration changes, and maintenance of traceability of relevant events in the infrastructure.

Keywords: Distributed Systems; Digital Infrastructures; Monitoring; Natural Resources

Computing Continuum Platform for River-Sea Systems

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River-sea systems sit at the intersection between inland waters, coastal waters, natural ecosystems, and human activity. The problematic access to the natural resources requires increased efforts for management and optimization. Furthermore, the management of these systems poses challenges, mainly related to real-time monitoring and early warning, due to the distributed nature of the sensing environments, connectivity gaps, unreliable networks, and heterogeneous data sources. So we do not only have to collect data from river-sea systems, but also to dynamically manage where data are processed, stored, validated, secured, and transformed into decisions across the IoT-edge-cloud-continuum. Hence, there is a need for a computing continuum platform to manage and monitor these systems. Therefore, we propose a computing continuum platform that includes an interoperable data platform connected to national infrastructures, with a strong focus on the efficient and sustainable use of natural resources.

Keywords: Computing Continuum; Digital Platform; River-Sea Systems

Digital Twin Framework for River-Sea Systems: A Hybrid Machine Learning and Rule-Based Water Quality Classification Approach

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River-sea systems face growing pressure from pollution and human activity, making water quality monitoring increasingly complex. While digital twins and machine learning offer promising solutions for environmental management, raw datasets often suffer from poor data quality and misalignment with safety standards. This study develops an integrated approach to address these challenges within river-sea environments.

The research involved preprocessing and analyzing a water quality dataset to verify the authenticity and consistency of existing labels. This pipeline serves as the data-ingestion core of the digital twin, ensuring that the virtual model accurately reflects physical reality. Multiple machine learning algorithms were tested and compared in terms of classification performance, robustness, and suitability for environmental monitoring applications. The resulting models and datasets were further integrated into an interactive digital platform for visualization and analysis.

The system successfully corrected initial data errors, creating a reliable dataset for monitoring purposes. The evaluation showed that combining rule-based compliance with machine learning provides superior adaptability for handling complex, borderline data points.

Combining automated validation and predictive models within a digital twin architecture improves monitoring reliability. This interactive framework provides authorities with a scalable and practical tool for sustainable water resource management.

Keywords: Digital Twin; Hybrid Machine Learning; Water Quality

From Urban Digital Twins to River-Sea Supersites: A Multi-Scale Geospatial Framework for Integrated Environmental Monitoring

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Digital Twin technologies are increasingly employed to represent complex environmental systems; however, current implementations remain largely domain-specific, focusing either on urban environments or large-scale ocean systems. This fragmentation limits the capacity to analyze interactions across the river-sea continuum, where urban areas play a critical role as both drivers and receptors of environmental processes. This study proposes a multi-scale Digital Twin framework designed to support the development of River-Sea Supersites by integrating high-resolution urban geospatial data with hydrological and marine system representations.

The framework builds upon an operational urban Digital Twin developed using multi-sensor data acquisition, including UAV photogrammetry, mobile LiDAR SLAM, and GNSS RTK positioning. These datasets are processed to generate detailed three-dimensional representations, including orthophotos, digital surface models, dense point clouds, and textured meshes, integrated within a GIS-based environment. The methodology is extended toward river-sea systems through the incorporation of in-situ monitoring networks, satellite observations, and numerical modelling outputs, enabling the representation of dynamic environmental processes across spatial and temporal scales.

Results demonstrate that urban Digital Twins can function as high-resolution boundary conditions within river-sea system modelling, particularly for applications such as flood risk assessment, pollutant transport analysis, and climate-driven scenario simulations. The proposed framework enables the integration of heterogeneous data sources into a unified digital environment, supporting advanced visualization, simulation, and decision-making processes.

The study contributes a scalable and transferable approach to Digital Twin development across the river-sea continuum, offering a conceptual and technical foundation for future implementations within the Danube-Black Sea system and similar environment.

Keywords: Digital Twin; UAV; LiDAR SLAM; 3D GIS

Implementing Analogue Modelling Capabilities for Source-To-Sink Research: A New Perspective

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The Danube-Black Sea continuum represents a complex source-to-sink (S2S) system where sediment routing is influenced by an interplay of tectonics, climate, and sea-level change. To date, Romanian research has relied heavily on field observations and numerical simulations.

This presentation outlines the principles of physical analogue modelling within the strategically implemented analogue laboratory at the Sulina Research Station from Danube Delta Supersite, highlighting its potential to provide experimental validation for large-scale morphodynamical processes.

We evaluate established laboratory protocols from international analogue modelling facilities (e.g., Experimental flumes and Tectonics Modelling Laboratory at Utrecht University) to define the technical requirements for a new S2S experimental setup. The methodology focuses on scaling of fluvial and deltaic systems, utilizing subsidence mechanisms, controlled discharge systems, and synthetic sediment analogues. By reviewing case studies from leading experimental laboratories, we identify the monitoring techniques (such as 3D photogrammetry and PIV) necessary to replicate the unique conditions in a sedimentary basin.

Drawing on benchmark examples from recent literature, we demonstrate how analogue experiments can successfully isolate variables—such as rate of sedimentation or subsidence. These examples serve as a "proof of concept" for the upcoming lab, illustrating how physical models can visualize the transfer of sediment from the upstream Danube to the deep-sea fans of the Black Sea.

Establishing an analogue modelling facility at the Sulina Research Station, the station the Institute of Geodynamics is responsible for, will provide a unique experimental platform for the DANUBIUS-RI framework. This infrastructure will enable researchers to integrate predictive, experimental models into the national research workflow, to better address "Sediment Balance" priorities and contribute to a more robust "Digital Twin" of the Danube-Black Sea system.

Keywords: Analogue Modelling; S2S; Danube-Black Sea

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Revisiting Reproducibility in Federated Learning across the Edge-Cloud Continuum: From Simulation to Cloud-Native Scheduling for Environmental Applications

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Federated Learning (FL) is increasingly deployed across the Edge-Cloud Continuum to support distributed AI applications operating on heterogeneous and geographically dispersed infrastructures. While simulation remains the dominant approach for evaluating FL systems, reproducing the behavior of real-world deployments remains challenging due to hardware heterogeneity, dynamic network conditions, orchestration overheads, and scheduling decisions. Existing reproducibility studies mainly focus on isolated Edge or cluster environments and rarely consider cloud-native infrastructures and scheduling mechanisms that are central to modern distributed systems.

In this paper, we extend previous work on FL reproducibility by introducing a methodology for evaluating and reproducing FL experiments across simulation, emulation, cloud, and real-world deployments. Beyond model convergence and execution latency, our approach investigates the reproducibility of scheduling strategies, resource allocation policies, and system-level behaviors across heterogeneous infrastructures.

To validate the methodology, we develop a new environmental monitoring use-case based on real sensor measurements collected from the Danube Delta ecosystem. The application trains distributed forecasting models using federated learning over heterogeneous Edge and Cloud resources while integrating real monitoring traces representative of environmental sensing infrastructures. We evaluate multiple deployment settings spanning clusters, Raspberry Pi Edge devices, and cloud-native platforms, and analyze the impact of scheduling policies on training performance, communication overhead, and resource utilization.

Our results show that simulation is effective for reproducing model-level metrics, while emulation and cloud-native deployments are required to accurately reproduce system-level behaviors and scheduling effects. We further identify the strengths and limitations of different experimental infrastructures for evaluating FL workflows and derive a set of practical recommendations for reproducible experimentation across the Computing Continuum.

Keywords: Monitoring; Federated Learning; Reproducibility

A Multi-Level Data Preprocessing Solution for Environmental Sensor Data Integration in Digital Twin Environments

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Digital Twin systems are a core infrastructure for real-time representation and visualization of data collected from sensor networks. However, in the context of monitoring the evolution of environmental parameters, the raw data produced by these sensors are frequently affected by quality issues arising during the acquisition process, which compromise the reliability of any subsequent data modelling or integration processes. Quality data remain the main priority which motivates the need for structured preprocessing approaches prior to data integration.

In this context, this paper proposes a structured preprocessing algorithm designed to systematically resolve the quality issues identified in the accompanying quality report, with the aim of enhancing data usability. The proposed workflow operates across three distinct processing levels including physical boundary validation, structural consolidation and temporal grid reconstruction. Firstly, technically invalid values are discarded while preserving temporal integrity. Next, structural issues are resolved through aggregation and deduplication and finally, in the last level, irregular frequencies are corrected through custom temporal reconstruction, while missing values are addressed through a differentiated imputation strategy based on the nature and extent of each gap.

A significant reduction in data quality issues was demonstrated across all addressed categories, by validating the algorithm against real-world environmental datasets. The processed datasets constitute a valid reference for monitoring environmental parameters, being suitable for integration into Digital Twin system modelling pipelines.

The proposed method represents a reproducible and scalable preprocessing workflow designed for sensor-based datasets. The resulting data accurately reflect the physical environment and, through a structured approach to data quality, it can serve as a reliable reference point for subsequent analytical workflows including the training of machine learning models to support decision-making in environmental monitoring.

Keywords: Data Preprocessing; Environmental Sensor; Digital Twin

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Agentic ETL Pipeline for Harmonising and Visualising Romanian Bathing-Water Quality Data

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Romanian bathing-water quality data are publicly available but fragmented across national, county, and European publication channels, with no single machine-readable national API for sample-level measurements. This limits timely comparison of microbiological water quality across bathing sites and makes longitudinal analysis difficult. An automated, source-aware workflow is therefore needed to transform scattered public-health publications into reusable surveillance data.

This work aims to design and prototype an ETL and agentic AI-assisted pipeline for collecting, harmonising, validating, and visualising official bathing-water quality data in Romania. The intended output is a dashboard-ready analytical layer that supports temporal evolution, latest-sample screening, site-level comparison, and transparent data-quality review.

We designed a crawler and extraction pipeline targeting official Romanian and European sources, including Ministry of Health bathing-water lists, county public-health directorate publications, INSP methodology and reports, and EEA/EMODnet harmonised registry and status datasets. Structured DSP Constanta .xls sampling files are treated as the primary machine-readable source, while semi-structured Tulcea .docx, .doc, and .pdf bulletins are routed through heuristic extraction and manual-review queues. Extracted records are standardised into three linked layers: a bathing-site registry, a long-form measurement table, and an annual classification/status table. Core indicators are normalised to *Escherichia coli* and intestinal enterococci in cfu/100mL, with provenance, parsing confidence, quality-control flags, and site reconciliation against European identifiers and coordinates.

The prototype architecture identified DSP Constanta as the strongest machine-readable source for recent sample-level data and EMODnet/EEA as the most reliable backbone for harmonised site metadata and historical status. Pilot extraction from recent Constanta sampling rounds supports site-level temporal summaries, latest-sample screening, and map-based visualisation. The workflow also exposes structural limitations, especially mixed publication formats and inconsistent Tulcea coverage, which are handled through explicit review queues rather than silent imputation.

An agentic ETL approach can transform fragmented public-health publications into a reproducible bathing-water monitoring dataset and dashboard-ready analytical layer. Separating raw measurements, site registry data, and official annual classification is essential to avoid conflating single-sample alerts with regulatory status. This approach provides a practical foundation for longitudinal surveillance, data-quality auditing, and future Romania-wide environmental health dashboards.

Keywords: Bathing Water Quality; ETL; Agentic AI; Environmental Surveillance; Dashboard
The authors declare no conflict of interest.

State of the Art Overview in Digital Twins for River-Sea Systems from a Multi-Modal Data Fusion and Machine Learning Perspective

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Managing complex river-sea continuums presents a gap in the integration of real-time structural stability monitoring with dynamic, environmental forecasting. Current monitoring techniques often fail to capture the complex interaction between large-scale hydrotechnical infrastructure and extreme climatic events. This presents timely as the priorities of the DANUBIUS-RI-2 project imply the use of high-resolution digital representations to mitigate risks in zones such as the Iron Gates supersite. Furthermore, the recent adoption of Cloud-Native technologies in this domain is highlighted for its benefits in facilitating federated, scalable and reusable processing for Earth Observation (EO) data.

This study establishes a framework for a structural-hydrotechnical Digital Twin (DT) designed for river-sea supersites. Objectives include: (1) defining a multi-source architecture for fusing satellite InSAR/EGMS data with in-situ observations; (2) evaluating Machine Learning (ML) approaches for automating big Earth Observation data pre-processing; and (3) outlining the use of Cloud-Native technologies for scalable and reusable processing.

The methodology presented in this paper is based on identifying key features in similar Digital Twin models that rely on the use of Machine Learning approaches to perform fusion of InSAR data with in-situ observations. The study is focused on the context of Cloud-Native architectures with an emphasis on data standardization using modern specifications such as Spatio-Temporal Asset Catalog (STAC) or the European INSPIRE directive.

Our analysis shows that correlating InSAR with in-situ observations facilitates detection of minute structural deformations. Findings indicate Machine Learning driven data assimilation significantly reduces processing times for heterogeneous flows, facilitating near real-time simulations of flood events and structural stress. The investigation of Cloud-Native technologies reveals a rich software inventory that can be easily deployed for data discovery which in turn simplifies model training.

Structural-hydrotechnical Digital Twins are essential for resilient infrastructure management. Practical implications include a standardized roadmap for European infrastructures to bridge civil engineering and environmental science.

Keywords: Digital Twin; Machine Learning; Cloud-Native

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Towards a Digital Twin of the Romanian Black Sea Coastal Zone: Integrating Direct Measurements, Remote Sensing and Numerical Modelling

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The Romanian Black Sea coast is currently undergoing significant morphodynamic changes driven by large-scale interventions, including beach nourishment and the construction or dismantling of coastal protection structures, particularly along the southern sector. These modifications, superimposed on a coastline whose protection infrastructure is over half a century old, call for updated, high-resolution and integrated knowledge to support coastal management, hazard mitigation and Blue Economy development. At present, no unified, FAIR-compliant system integrates direct measurements, remote sensing and numerical modelling at the scale of the Romanian coast.

A multi-component approach is being implemented, combining seasonal field campaigns along representative beach sectors of the deltaic and southern coast, including DGPS shoreline and cross-shore profiling, UAV photogrammetry, updated bathymetric surveys and sedimentological sampling; satellite remote sensing based on Copernicus missions; numerical modelling of coastal hydrodynamics and wave propagation using the SHYFEM 3D and SWAN models; and the design of a FAIR-compliant data catalogue and geoportal, supported by a dedicated CKAN + GeoServer instance for geospatial publication.

Work to date has produced updated datasets on shoreline position, beach morphology, bathymetry and sediment composition along nourished southern sectors and pilot deltaic sites, capturing seasonal variability and the response of the coast to recent interventions. A FAIR-compliant data catalogue and an associated geoportal are in advanced development phase, integrating the generated data within a unified architecture and providing interactive GIS visualization of the available datasets.

This work provides the basis for a Digital Twin of the Romanian coastal zone, offering a replicable approach for coastal monitoring, hazard identification and Blue Economy planning in the Black Sea basin, and aligning the Romanian coast with European DTO initiatives.

Keywords: Digital Twin; Black Sea; Coastal Zone Management

Data Collection and Management Solution for IoT Sensors Based on LoRaWAN Communication

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In this paper we present a low-code solution for data collection and management for IoT sensors based on LoRaWAN communication.

The presented solution enables the usage of various free/open-source software components for the management of a standalone LoRaWAN network and enables long-term data storage using specialized Time-Series Databases. The solution also leverages Knative Eventing as a backend solution for enabling serverless processing of events and builds on top of the ROCS/EOCube.ro project.

The observability part of the solution is accomplished using a well-known open-source solution called Grafana and the extensibility of the current implementation is provided through flow-based data management (using Node-Red).

The work addresses three objectives: (i) design a modular, low-code architecture for collecting and managing IoT sensor data over a standalone LoRaWAN network; (ii) integrate free and open-source components - including a LoRaWAN Network Server, MQTT broker, time-series database, flow-based middleware, and a serverless eventing backend - into a coherent end-to-end pipeline aligned with the ROCS/EOCube.ro platform; and (iii) provide flexible observability and extensibility so that domain users can adapt data flows, dashboards, and alerts without writing custom code; (iv) provide the foundational blocks for the data-gathering component of a Digital Twin platform for long-distance observations without 4/5G coverage.

The solution is built around ThingsStack as the LoRaWAN Network Server, which forwards uplink messages via MQTT to Node-RED. Node-RED flows decode sensor payloads, enrich them with device metadata, and route the resulting time-series records into InfluxDB. Event-driven processing is delegated to Knative Eventing, which dispatches decoded messages to serverless functions for tasks such as payload validation, derived-metric computation, and downstream notification, building on the ROCS/EOCube.ro project for the underlying cloud-native runtime. Grafana connects to InfluxDB to provide dashboards, ad-hoc exploration, and threshold-based alerting. All components are containerised and orchestrated on Kubernetes so the stack can be deployed either on a single edge gateway or scaled across cloud-native infrastructure.

The resulting pipeline has been deployed in pilot configurations collecting environmental measurements from LoRaWAN sensor nodes, with payloads decoded and persisted in InfluxDB at sub-second latency from gateway ingest. Node-RED flows proved effective for onboarding new sensor types without code changes, requiring only the addition of a decoder node and a routing rule. Knative Eventing allowed processing logic to be added and scaled independently of the ingest path, with serverless functions activated on demand and scaled to zero when idle, which kept the resource footprint low between sensor uplinks. Grafana dashboards expose both real-time telemetry and long-term aggregates, and operators have used the alerting layer to detect device drop-outs and out-of-range readings. The low-code surface lowered the integration effort for non-developer users, while the open-source stack and the ROCS/EOCube.ro foundation avoided vendor lock-in.

Combining a standalone LoRaWAN network with flow-based middleware, a time-series database, a serverless eventing backend, and an open dashboarding layer yields a practical, extensible foundation for IoT data collection in research and operational settings. Anchoring the deployment on the ROCS/EOCube.ro cloud-native platform makes the architecture a natural building block for Digital Twin applications in the DANUBIUS-RI context, where heterogeneous environmental sensors must be integrated, observed, and exposed to downstream models. Future work will focus on edge-side preprocessing, federated deployment across supersites, and tighter integration between the Knative-based processing layer and cloud-native Earth-observation services.

Keywords: Digital Twin; Edge; Cloud-Native

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Romanian Participation in EU Framework Programmes on River-Sea Systems Research. Background and Opportunities in the Context of DANUBIUS-ERIC

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Romania has participated in the EU Framework Programmes since 1998, enjoying same rights and obligations as an EU member states. Furthermore, ERDF resources have been available since Romania joined the EU in 2007, benefiting of additional resources available to build up or consolidate its research infrastructures. DANUBIUS-RI has been acknowledged as a top priority since 2015 by both the Romanian government and the Romanian Academy, with significant funding earmarked for this matter. Currently, a project budgeted with about 130 million EUR is being implemented at Murighiol (Romania), which will allow DANUBIUS-ERIC to operate at its full capacity. While one of the critical challenges in the future is building up a strong, highly skilled human resource base that will enable researchers to operate in the future with state of the art equipment, complementary with European fellows, the focus in the next years is to exploit all possible funding opportunities that will consolidate DANUBIUS-RI its scientific capacity and, in the long term, enable it to operate as a global R&D infrastructure.

This aim of this study is to assess the Romanian participation to R&D projects in the River-Seas systems related topics listed in the EU framework programmes (since 2014) and to identify future opportunities that should allow consolidation of scientific capacity, considering also the important investments is R&D facilities. This could be considered as a possible starting point to a strategy to prioritize resources to achieves objectives stated in the scientific research and innovation agenda (DANUBIUS-SRIA) of DANUBIUS-RI.

Data on Romanian participation will be extracted from EU Dashboard, which provides accurate information on all grant agreements for any participating countries. Additionally, the existing funding opportunities from ERDF (Operational Programs for R&I) will be scanned. Data will be aggregated and matched with the scientific areas mentioned in DANUBIUS-SRIA.

The main outcomes of this study will be: a) Romanian participation in the EU framework programmes since 2014 on River-Sea systems research topics, and b) the identification of potential directions and opportunities where DANUBIUS-RI scientific communities may apply for funding in order to implement the SRIA and expand and consolidate the human resource pool

Results and conclusions from this study will be made publicly available to the whole scientific community interested and active in various research topics related to River-Sea systems. As project proposals (research & innovation actions) cannot be submitted by only one organization it will attract R&I organizations also from other EU Member states and associated countries

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DANUBIUS-RO 2026 marks the inaugural national scientific conference dedicated to interdisciplinary research on River-Sea Systems, with a particular focus on the Danube–Black Sea continuum.

Organised within the research framework of DANUBIUS-RI, the International Centre for Advanced Studies on River-Sea Systems, the conference brings together scientists, practitioners, and policymakers to share state-of-the-art research, exchange expertise, and address pressing environmental and societal challenges.

The conference addresses key topics including water and sediment dynamics, biodiversity, climate change, pollution, digital technologies, and integrated solutions for the sustainable management of complex river-sea systems.

DANUBIUS-RO-2

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